

Visible-Light Photocatalysis: Does it make a difference in Organic Synthesis?

Leyre Marzo, Santosh K. Pagire, Oliver Reiser, and Burkhard König**

Dedication ((optional))

Frontispiece Graphic
(18.5 cm in diameter)

Abstract: Visible light photocatalysis has evolved over the last decade into a widely used method in organic synthesis. For many important transformations, such as cross-coupling reactions, α -amino functionalizations, cycloadditions, ATRA reactions, or fluorinations, photocatalytic variants have been reported. To support chemists selecting photocatalytic methods for their synthesis, we compare in this review classical and photocatalytic procedures for selected classes of reactions and highlight their advantages and limitations. In many cases, the photocatalytic reactions proceed under milder reaction conditions, typically at room temperature, and stoichiometric reagents are replaced by simple oxidants or reductants, like air, oxygen, or amines.

Does visible light photocatalysis make a difference in organic synthesis? The prospect to shuttle electrons back and forth to substrates and intermediates or to selectively transfer energy through a visible light absorbing photocatalyst holds the promise to improve current protocols in radical chemistry and to open up new avenues by accessing reactive species hitherto unknown especially by merging photocatalysis with organo- or metal catalysis.

1. Introduction

The beginning of the 21st century has witnessed a dramatic increase of research in the area of visible light photocatalysis, documented by a rapidly increasing number of publications in the field since 2008. Clearly, using visible light as a reagent in combination with catalysts is attractive for developing efficient and selective chemical transformations. Nature impressively demonstrates the power of photosynthesis by converting carbon dioxide and water to carbohydrates and oxygen, a process that is so far unrivaled by any man-made chemical procedure.

With the current developments in visible light photocatalysis ongoing, in this review we aim to support chemists in selecting suitable methods for their synthesis needs. We discuss photocatalytic reactions in the order of bond formations they achieve and illuminate the level of innovation that is being made. We highlight groundbreaking synthetic transformations and point out where photocatalysis is just a different way to carry out already known radical processes.

The term photocatalysis may be misleading at the first glance, as light, photons, are used as a reagent, in most cases in large excess and not catalytic. *Photocatalysis* describes transformations that require light as an energy input to proceed and typically use catalytic amounts of light absorbing photocatalysts, such as metal complexes of organic dyes.

One principle mode of action in visible light photocatalysis is to induce an electron transfer to or from a substrate, thus generating radical anions or cations (or neutral radicals when cationic or anionic starting materials are used), which are often followed by the extrusion of a leaving group to overall form a neutral radical as the reactive species that initiates a chemical transformation. Such reactions are described as *photoredox catalysis*. Using appropriate initiators, such radicals can also

be generated in a thermal process. A photoredox catalyst can therefore just act as an initiator for a radical chain process, or if the catalyst is further involved in the catalytic cycle, affect the overall outcome of a chemical transformation. After light excitation of the photocatalyst, four pathways of a single electron transfer from or to a substrate are possible (**Scheme 1a**): Oxidative (**1.**) or reductive (**2.**) quenching of the excited state of the photocatalysts. Note that these electron transfer steps require a $\Delta G \leq 0$ due to the short lifetime of the excited state. Photocatalytic cycles that include an oxidation and a reduction step and do not require sacrificial oxidants or reductants, are called redox-neutral. Alternatively, the photocatalysts is quenched by a sacrificial electron donor (typical an amine or ascorbic acid) or an electron acceptor (typical air oxygen or peroxydisulfate) and the reduced or oxidized photocatalyst can oxidize (**3.**) or reduce (**4.**) a substrate in a ground state reaction. If this electron transfer is followed by a fast and irreversible reaction step of the substrate, endergonic electron transfers with $\Delta G > 0$ (up to 500 mV) are possible.

Proton-coupled electron transfer extends the range of substrates that can be reduced or oxidized (**Scheme 1b**; **5.** and **6.**). Photoinitiated redox steps can be coupled with metal- (**8.**) or organo-catalyzed (**7.**) reactions (**Scheme 1c**), which is called synergistic or dual catalysis. Transition metal intermediates trap and stabilize transient radical species, generated by photoredox steps, making them available for synthesis. Dual photo-organo catalysis allows, among other strategies, to control the stereoselectivity of reactions using chiral organocatalysts.

The second mode of action is that a *photosensitizer* transfer's energy to a substrate, which itself is not able to absorb light at a given wavelength (**Scheme 1d**, **9.**). This mode of sensitization has a long tradition in synthetic photochemistry. However, the combination of high power visible light emitting LEDs and the discovery of catalysts, which can carry out energy transfer processes efficiently, hold the promise for new transformations to be discovered. Last but not least, there is an increasing number of reports on visible light photocatalysis of UV absorbing substrates without added photocatalysts. *In situ* formation of electron donor-acceptor complexes, which show long wavelength absorption leading to charge separation, is the mode of action in such cases (**Scheme 1e**, **10.**)

In this review, we compare chemical transformations that can either be carried out by visible light photocatalysis or by non-photochemical alternatives. Selected examples are chosen that allow a close analogy for a given transformation. Yields and substrate scope, catalyst turnover, environmentally benign and readily available reagents and catalysts, reaction time and temperature are typical benchmark parameters that allow an evaluation of different protocols. The greatest value of visible light photo catalyzed reactions is arguably found for processes that do not have a thermal counterpart, and both, selective electron and energy transfer to non-adsorbing molecules from light adsorbing photocatalysts have opened exciting synthetic avenues in organic synthesis.

We have organized our review by the type of bond being formed by the transformation and specific reaction classes, such as cycloadditions, ATRA reactions or decarboxylations. As a subcategory we use the type of radical, which is initially generated as the reactive intermediate, and the atom hybridization in the product bond. Some transformations can be assigned into different categories, e.g. sp^3 - sp^2 carbon-carbon bond formation or decarboxylative coupling; we indicate this by cross-referencing.

Our survey does not aim to be comprehensive, which would be beyond any scope that can be covered. We focus on reactions that are widely used in organic synthesis and for which thermal and photocatalytic variants have been reported. Within these reaction classes,

[*] Dr. L. Marzo, Dr. S. K. Pagire, Prof. Dr. O. Reiser, Prof. Dr.

B. König

Institut für Organische Chemie, Universität Regensburg,

Universitätsstraße 31, 93053 Regensburg (Germany).

*E-mail: Burkhard.Koenig@chemie.uni-regensburg.de

*E-mail: Oliver.Reiser@chemie.uni-regensburg.de

we have selected typical, recent examples that illustrate the scope and limitations. We apologize to all researchers, who find their work not covered in our review, but a comprehensive discussion of all thermal and photocatalytic synthetic chemistry is beyond our possibilities. Our review focusses on the application of visible light photocatalysis to organic synthesis; mechanistic proposals for the individual reactions cannot be discussed in detail to keep this survey at a reasonable size. To provide the reader with an overview, Scheme 1 summarizes the most prominent mechanistic pathways of photocatalysis and synergistic photocatalysis. We refer in the discussion of the reaction to this overview chart and would furthermore like to draw the attention of the readers to the many excellent reviews on specific topics, including mechanistic proposals, in the field of visible light photocatalysis.^[1]

Scheme 1. General mechanisms of photoredox catalysis (a,b), synergistic catalysis (c), photosensitization (d) and excitation of donor-acceptor complexes (e) using visible light.

Scheme 2. Typical photoredox catalysts with their long wave absorption maximum and redox properties (all values against SCE).

We begin the overview with carbon-carbon bond formations ordered by the hybridization of the connected carbon atoms in the product; this structure allows the reader identifying suitable photocatalytic transformations during retrosynthetic analysis when planning the synthesis of a target compound. The next section covers carbon-heteroatom bond formations grouped by the type of heteroatom. This is followed by the important area of α -amino functionalization, for which visible light photocatalysis had a large impact. Decarboxylative coupling reactions, cycloadditions, and ATRA reactions are discussed

and we finish with fluorinations as a specific, but important transformation for which catalytic and photocatalytic methods exist. Readers, who hope for a final conclusion whether a thermal or a photocatalytic variant is superior, may be disappointed. Nevertheless, the main processes covered in this review are comparatively summarized in the supporting information attached to the article (Table S1). Moreover, due to space reasons, some examples that are mentioned along the review are explained in more detail in the supporting information, following the same organization as in the review. We discuss the key benchmark parameters, but scale, scope, starting materials and available equipment have to be considered in choosing the best conditions for a specific transformation.

Burkhard König received his Ph.D. in 1991 from the University of Hamburg. He continued his scientific education as a post-doctoral fellow with Prof. M. A. Bennett, Research School of Chemistry, Australian National University, Canberra, and Prof. B. M. Trost, Stanford University. Since 1999, he is a full professor of organic chemistry at the University of Regensburg. His current research interests are the development of synthetic methods in photoredox catalysis.

Oliver Reiser studied in Hamburg, Jerusalem and at UCLA. After postdoctoral research at IBM with Robert D. Miller and at Harvard University with David A. Evans, he began his independent career at the University of Göttingen. He moved to Stuttgart as associate professor and became a full professor of organic chemistry in 1997 at the University of Regensburg. His research interests center around synthesis and catalysis, including the development of new photo- and magnetic nanoparticle-supported catalysts.

Santosh K. Pagire obtained his M.Sc. degree in 2011 from the University of Pune, India. Afterward, he began his research training (2012-2013) at CSIR-NCL, Pune, India. Later, he received a full-time DAAD fellowship to conduct his Ph.D. studies in the group of Prof. Reiser at the University of Regensburg, Germany (2013-2017). His Ph.D. thesis was focused on applications of visible-light photocatalysis in organic synthesis.

Leyre Marzo received her Ph.D. in 2015 from the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Afterward, she joined the group of Prof. König at the University of Regensburg as an Alexander von Humboldt post-doctoral fellow where she is working in the field of photocatalysis. Her research interest focuses on the development of new synthetic methods using visible light photocatalysis.

2. Carbon-Carbon bond formation

2.1. sp^3 Carbon-centered radicals as reactive intermediate

2.1.1. Formation of products with Csp^3-Csp^3 bonds

In this section the reader will find a compilation of methodologies to form Csp^3-Csp^3 bonds from *in-situ* generated Csp^3 radicals. Due to the order in which we will discuss the reactions, some examples that yield Csp^3-Csp^3 bonds by a specific transformation, e.g. cycloaddition, ATRA reaction or decarboxylation are described in sections 4, 5, 6 and 7.

The development of new stereoselective methods to form Csp^3-Csp^3 bonds has attracted much interest in the scientific community and many reactions have been developed over the years. In this section of the review, we have collected the most representative photocatalytic approaches to form Csp^3-Csp^3 bonds in an enantioselective manner through sp^3 carbon-centered radicals as the key intermediate.

The use of samarium diiodide (SmI_2) as a reducing agent was reported for the first time 35 years ago by Kagan,^[2] and since then a large number of transformations utilizing this reagent have been developed.^[3] A representative transformation is the reduction of ketones to the corresponding ketyl radical followed by the intramolecular cyclization with activated double bonds, ketones, and imines affording cyclic derivatives through the formation of a Csp^3-Csp^3 bond (Scheme 3). In the presence of chiral ligands, the reaction can proceed enantio- or diastereoselective. Stoichiometric amounts of SmI_2 , being best synthesized *in situ*, are required. Photoredox catalysis provides an alternative method by substituting expensive reducing reagents, like SmI_2 , by milder and cheaper ones, such as Hantzsch ester.

Scheme 3. Csp^3-Csp^3 bond formation by SmI_2 and visible light photocatalysis.

The highly negative reduction potential of ketones does not allow their reduction by classic photocatalysts. However, Knowles and coworkers have demonstrated that concerted proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET) diminishes the energy required to access certain radical species that would be inaccessible by a sequential electron-proton transfer process.^[4] In 2013 they reported an intramolecular PCET-based methodology for the reductive coupling of ketones and Michael acceptors (Scheme 4, left; for a more detailed mechanisms, see Scheme 1b).^[5] Pre-equilibrium H-bond coordination between the phosphoric acid **7** and the ketone **1** facilitates the SET from the reduced photocatalyst (Ru(I)) to the ketone, forming the ketyl radical intermediate **5** that reacts intramolecularly with the electron-deficient olefin. Thus, an α -acyl radical is formed, which upon H-atom abstraction from 2-phenyldihydrobenzothiazoline **3** (BT) affords a mixture of *cis/trans* cyclopentanols **4** in moderate to excellent yields and diastereoselectivities (Scheme 4, left). Later, they applied this method to the synthesis of cyclic α -aminoalcohols **9** through a coupling reaction between ketyl radicals and a hydrazone moiety being present in the molecule.^[6] The intimate association of the chiral phosphoric acid **7** and the ketyl radical **5** during the C-C bond formation step gave rise to **9** in high yields and good enantioselectivities (Scheme 2, right).

Scheme 4. Intramolecular reductive coupling of ketones and Michael acceptors (left). Synthesis of cyclic α -aminoalcohols by visible light photocatalysis (right).

Traditionally, the use of chiral auxiliaries allows the α -alkylation of carbonyl compounds in good yields and high stereoselectivity. However, α -alkylation *via* $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ mechanism starting from alkyl halides is not possible in classic methodologies.^[7] Switching from ionic to radical chemistry, SOMO catalysis afforded an alternative α -alkylation method (Scheme 5).^[8] Combining organocatalysis with a stoichiometric oxidant, the nucleophilic character of the *in situ* generated enamine was unpoled, yielding an electrophilic enamine radical cation that could react with a larger variety of alkylating reagents. However the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ mechanistic approach limitation remained unsolved. Visible light photocatalysis has given a brilliant solution, since it allows the α -alkylation of carbonyl compounds using alkyl halides as starting materials, replace stoichiometric amounts of oxidants by reductively generating radicals from an appropriate precursor, and avoids the use of chiral auxiliaries with a chiral organocatalyst as the source of stereoselectivity in the reaction.

Scheme 5. General representation of SOMO- and photocatalysis.

The following schemes present reactions, which are unique to visible light photoredox catalysis. The first example of dual organo-photoredox catalysis was reported by MacMillan with the enantioselective α -alkylation of aldehydes **10** with α -bromo carbonyl compounds **11** (Scheme 6).^[9] In the key step, radical **16** is coupled with enamine **15** affording **14** in good enantioselectivities (Scheme 6; for a more detailed mechanism, see Scheme 1c). Subsequently, the scope of the reaction was expanded to trifluoromethylations,^[10] cyanoalkylations,^[11] benzylations,^[12] and related transformations.^[13,14] In addition, different combinations of visible light photocatalysts and organocatalysts have been developed.^[15]

Scheme 6. Enantioselective α -alkylation of aldehydes.

Melchiorre and coworkers have demonstrated that the presence of an external photocatalyst is not required for the stereoselective C-C bond formation using visible light (Scheme 7). They found that enamines formed by condensation of a chiral catalyst **18** and an aldehyde **10** react under visible light irradiation with benzyl bromides, overall achieving an enantioselective α -alkylation of aldehydes (Scheme 7a).^[16] Electron rich enamines form colored electron donor-acceptor complexes (EDA complexes) with electron deficient benzyl bromides or phenacyl bromides **17** in the ground state. Irradiation of the EDA complex **20** triggers an electron transfer (ET) from the enamine to the halide, ultimately generating radicals that are in close proximity and in a geometrically restricted chiral space (see **21**, Scheme 7a; for a general mechanism, see scheme 1e), forcing an enantioselective C-C bond formation. Enamines can also act as photo-initiators themselves (absorption maxima > 400 nm) without EDA complex formation.^[17] This way, the direct enantioselective alkylation of non-aromatic aldehydes **10** with bromomalonates **23** was achieved (Scheme 7b).^[18] Moreover, starting from α -substituted enals **22**, alkylation in the γ -position through a dienamine is possible, affording adducts of type **26** in good yield, but lower enantioselectivity.

The same group reported the enantioselective β -alkylation of enals **27** mediated by visible light (Scheme 7c).^[19] They demonstrated that the iminium ion formed by condensation between an enal and the prolinol derivative **29** is able to oxidize alkyl silanes **28** upon excitation to generate alkyl radical **31**, which couples with the β -enaminal radical **32** (Scheme 7c).

In a conceptually different approach, Meggers and coworkers have designed new chiral [Ir]-complexes that act as photoredox catalysts and as chiral Lewis acid responsible for the asymmetric induction in the C-C bond formation (see SI, Scheme S1 for more detail).^[20,21]

Scheme 7. Direct enantioselective α - and γ -alkylations of aldehydes driven by chiral amines (a, b). Enantioselective β -alkylation of enals mediated by visible light (c).

2.1.2. Formation of products with Csp³-Csp² bonds

In this section we discuss methods to form Csp³-Csp² bonds from *in-situ* generated Csp³ radicals. More examples involving Csp³-Csp² bond formation can be found in sections 4, 5, and 7.

Palladium and nickel catalyzed reactions, such as Stille,^[22] Kumada,^[23] Suzuki-Miyaura,^[24] Negishi^[25] couplings, as well as the cross coupling of organolithium reagents,^[26] have been broadly employed for Csp³-Csp² bond formations (Scheme 8). In particular the Stille coupling tolerates many functional groups, including alcohols, ketones, enones, esters, lactones, nitriles, nitro groups, and epoxides, and beside aryl and vinyl halide, also acyl halides are suitable coupling partners. The olefin stereochemistry of alkenyl-halides or alkenyl-tin species is retained in the reaction.

Nevertheless, these methods require a stoichiometric amount of an organometallic reagent, necessary for the transmetalation step of the *in situ* generated organopalladium or organonickel coupling partner. An attractive alternative consists of the photocatalytic generation of alkyl radicals, which can be trapped with an organonickel species, thus avoiding the high energy transition state associated with the transmetalation step.

Scheme 8. Cross-coupling by classical and photocatalytic methods.

The following example illustrates how the photocatalytic pathway is able to overcome a limitation of the classic conditions in the Suzuki-Miyaura cross coupling. Based on the oxidation potential reported for potassium organotrifluoroborates,^[27] Molander and coworkers developed a photoredox/nickel catalyzed cross-coupling reaction between primary alkyl organotrifluoroborates **33a** and aryl bromides **34** (Scheme 9a).^[28] Trifluoroborates **33a** are oxidized by the Ir-F photocatalyst **35** under visible light irradiation to generate an alkyl radical that adds to the ArNi^{III}Br complex (formed after oxidative addition of **34** to Ni⁰), generating a Ni^{III}-alkyl complex. Subsequent reductive elimination yields the desired cross-coupling product **36a** in good yield. Different primary alkyl trifluoroborates, benzylic trifluoroborates bearing different substituents in the aromatic ring, including non-protected protic functional groups, as well as differently substituted aryl and heteroaryl bromides could be employed in the process (Scheme 9a). Compared to the classic Suzuki-Miyaura coupling, the mild reaction conditions and the improved functional group tolerance are advantageous.^[24] The non-photochemical Pd-catalyzed cross-coupling of secondary alkylboron reagents gave a mixture of regioisomers due to the formation of a π -bond Pd-olefin complex via β -hydride elimination.^[29] The use of nickel catalysis avoids the β -hydride elimination, thus overcoming the regioselectivity problem, and in combination with photoredox catalysis allowed to expand the method to un-activated secondary alkyltrifluoroborates (Scheme 9b).^[30] Likewise, symmetric and unsymmetric secondary alkyltrifluoroborates **33b** underwent regioselective coupling with a large variety of aryl and heteroaryl bromides **34** (Scheme 9b).^[30]

Scheme 9. Cross-coupling of alkyl trifluoroborates with aryl halides.

Although excellent results were obtained with potassium organotrifluoroborates, these reagents have drawbacks such as low solubility, high oxidation potential, and the problematic release of BF₃ after photo-oxidation or the need to employ a base. This prompted the exploration of new alkyl radical precursors that might avoid these limitations. Bis-catecholato silicates **37** are not hygroscopic, bench stable, and can be readily prepared from inexpensive trimethoxy-alkylsilanes. Moreover, they are more easily oxidized (+0.34 V to +0.89 V vs SCE)^[31] than organotrifluoroborates (>1.1 V vs SCE).^[27,32]

REVIEW

Fensterbank and coworkers described the cross coupling reaction of primary alkyl potassium bis-catecholato silicates **37a** with aryl and heteroaryl halides **34** using dual metallophotoredox catalysis (Scheme 10a).^[33] DFT calculations suggested that a SET from the catechol moiety to the metal center of the photocatalyst takes place, weakening the C-Si bond and favoring its fragmentation and the formation of the relatively stable alkyl radical. At the same time, Molander and coworkers utilized alkylammonium alkylbis(catecholato)silicates **37b**, whose solubility properties can be modulated depending on the nature of the ammonium counter-ion, in the coupling with aryl bromides (Scheme 10b).^[34] They focused their efforts on challenging examples, such as substrates resistant to oxidative addition (e.g. 4-bromoanisole), alkyl silicates bearing unprotected amines or compounds bearing unprotected protic functional groups (e.g. amides, alcohols, etc.). Furthermore, vinylhalides are suitable coupling partners for alkylsilicates (Scheme 10 b),^[35] thus overcoming a limitation of trifluoroborates.

Scheme 10. Cross-coupling reaction of alkyl potassium bis-catecholato silicates with aryl, heteroaryl and vinyl halides.

MacMillan and coworkers reported a photoredox-nickel-catalyzed cross-coupling reaction between alkyl bromides and aryl bromides, representing commercially available, bench stable and easy to handle reagents (for more detail on this approach see SI, Scheme S2).^{[36], [37]} All examples discussed so far require pre-functionalized substrates. Molander and coworkers recently developed a photochemical C-H arylation catalyzed by nickel via $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds activation.^[38] The triplet state of a diaryl ketone is able to activate $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds by H-atom transfer (HAT),^[39] which is used in a tri-catalytic cycle involving $[\text{Ir}]$ **35**, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone **43**. The method allows the coupling of a large variety of aryl and heteroaryl bromides **34** with **42** (Scheme 11) and has some advantages compared to the classical arylation of tetrahydrofurans,^[40] such as the use of the more stable aryl bromides instead of aryl boronic acids. However, both approaches require the use of the $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ partner in large excess, i.e. as the solvent in the reaction. In parallel, Doyle reported the $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ arylation starting from aryl chlorides,^[41] while MacMillan developed the arylation of $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)$ centers α to an amino group with different aryl halides, in which the $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ partner can be used in lower amounts.^[42]

Scheme 11. A photochemical C-H arylation catalyzed by nickel, via $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds activation.

2.2. sp^2 Carbon-centered radicals as reactive intermediates

2.2.1. Formation of products with $\text{Csp}^2\text{-Csp}^3$ bonds

In this section the reader will find a compilation of methods to create $\text{Csp}^2\text{-Csp}^3$ bonds from *in-situ* generated Csp^2 radicals. Additional examples that also involve $\text{Csp}^2\text{-Csp}^3$ bond formations are discussed in sections 5.2 and 7.2

The Meerwein arylation addition reaction is a classic approach for the formation $\text{Csp}^2\text{-Csp}^2$ bonds.^[43] Aryldiazonium salts are reduced by different metal salts to aryl radicals, which are trapped by an olefin yielding an alkyl radical (Scheme 12). Depending on substrates and reaction conditions, different termination pathways are conceivable, among them the incorporation of a third reaction partner $[\text{Y}]$ yielding the final product. Such reactions have been extensively explored and a broad product scope is available. Photocatalytic reduction of the diazonium salt represents a valuable alternative to redox active metal salts affording similar or superior results.

Scheme 12. $\text{Csp}^2\text{-Csp}^3$ bond formation.

König and coworkers developed an efficient visible light photocatalyzed α -arylation of enol acetates **46** with aryl diazonium salts **45** (Scheme 13).^[44] Reduction of aryl diazonium salts by $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ generates the corresponding aryl radical and the strong oxidant $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{3+}$. The subsequent addition of the aryl radical to enol acetate **46** gives a radical intermediate that is re-oxidized by $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{3+}$, affording a β -aryl-carbocation intermediate **48**, which reacts with nucleophiles present in the reaction mixture yielding products **47**.

Scheme 13. Visible light photocatalyzed α -arylation of enol acetates.

The scope was extended to a three-component process, trapping the carbocation intermediate with nitriles^[45] or dimethylformamide,^{[46], [47]} and the scope of the reaction could be expanded by combining photoredox and gold catalysis (for more detail see SI, Scheme S3 and S4).^{[48], [49]}

Apart from aryl diazonium salts, other compounds can serve as precursors of aryl radicals, and especially diaryliodonium salts^[50] **49** have been applied in different arylation methods.^[51] Greaney and coworkers first reported the use in the photocatalyzed oxy arylation of styrenes **50** (Scheme 14a),^[52] combining $\text{Ir}(\text{bpy})_3$ **51** and $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2$ as the catalytic system, what avoided side reactions such as polymerizations. A year later, Glorius and coworkers reported that $[\text{Ph}_3\text{PAu}]\text{NTf}_2$

REVIEW

is also an efficient cocatalyst, obtaining the corresponding arylated ethers **53** in moderate to excellent yields (Scheme 14b).^[53]

Scheme 14. Visible light induced methoxy and oxy arylation of styrenes.

2.2.2 Formation of products with Csp²-Csp² bonds

Csp²-Csp² bond formations are typically achieved by palladium and nickel catalyzed cross-coupling reactions (Scheme 15). Photocatalytic methods represent a good alternative to the classic approaches, because the reactions proceed at room temperature and inexpensive organic molecules (dyes) as photocatalyst might replace more costly transition metal catalysts. Moreover, as coupling partners unfunctionalized arenes can often be used, complementing the field of transition metal catalyzed arene coupling reactions that proceed by C-H activation.^[54]

Scheme 15. Csp²-Csp² bond formation.

Aryl diazonium salts are suitable reagents for photocatalytic Csp²-X cross coupling reactions.^[55] After the first example by Cano-Yelo and Deronzier of a photocatalyzed Pschorr reaction with [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ as photoredox catalyst reported 30 years ago,^[56] Sanford and coworkers reported in 2011 the substrate-directed C-H arylation reaction by combining palladium catalysis with visible light photocatalysis (Scheme 16).^[57] As a key step, it was proposed that an aryl radical, generated from **45** by a photoinduced electron transfer step, would combine with a Pd(II)-complex formed by C-H activation with **54** to give rise to a Pd(III)-intermediate. Further oxidation of the latter to a Pd(IV)-intermediate with concomitant regeneration of the Ru-photocatalyst can then yield the product **55** by a final reductive elimination and concurrent release of Pd(II).

Scheme 16. The ligand-directed C-H arylation reaction with aryl diazonium salts.

König and coworkers reported the C-H arylation of heteroarenes **56** with aryl diazonium salts **45** using eosin Y **57** (an organic dye) as a photoredox catalyst with green light (Scheme 17; for a detailed mechanism see Scheme 1a).^[58] Electron rich heteroarenes are especially suitable coupling partners, but *ortho*-nitrobenzene also gave the cross-coupling product **59** in 50% yield.

Scheme 17. C-H arylation of heteroarenes using aryl diazonium salts and eosin Y as a photocatalyst.

Apart from aromatic or heteroaromatic compounds, unsaturated compounds such as acetylenes **62** proved to be excellent trapping reagents of aryl radicals. The photocatalytic radical annulation of *ortho*-methylthio-arene diazonium salts with alkynes in the presence of eosin Y **57** as photocatalyst and green light afforded benzothiophenes **63** as a single regioisomer (Scheme 18).^[59] Electron-donating or withdrawing groups in the diazonium salt are tolerated, as well as mono and disubstituted acetylenes, providing the desired benzothiophenes **63** in moderate to good yields.

Scheme 18. The photocatalytic radical annihilation of aryl diazonium salts with alkynes by eosin Y photocatalyst.

The Meerwein arylation reaction has been applied for the arylation of various unsaturated compounds with transition metal salts, but yields are only moderate and the formation of side products is observed.^[60] By using chloride containing ionic liquids as promoting agents, reaction yields increased.^[61] Visible light photocatalysis affords an alternative approach for the arylation of alkenes, alkynes, and enones in good yields, but the reaction is limited to activated compounds such as coumarins, quinones, styrenes, and phenyl acetylenes (Scheme 19a).^[62] Later, Yu and coworkers were able to extend the photo Meerwein arylation to ene-carbamates and enamides **66** (Scheme 19b).^[63]

Scheme 19. The photocatalytic Meerwein arylation of alkenes with aryl diazonium salts (a). The photo Meerwein arylation to enecarbamates and enamides (b).

In 2014, König and coworkers reported the first con-PET (*consecutive-photoinduced-electron-transfer*) process able to reduce aryl bromides and chlorides.^[64] In a typical PET process, the photocatalyst absorbs a photon by irradiation with visible light reaching an excited state that is able to accept one electron from a sacrificial electron donor to form a radical anion. This radical anion transfers the electron to a substrate and returns to its ground state. In the con-PET processes, the intermediate radical anion (being stable and colored) is able to absorb a second photon, reaching a new excited state of higher energy that allows now the reduction of aryl bromides and chlorides.

Perylene bisimides **69** (Scheme 20) are a class of photostable organic dyes, which are able to perform a con-PET process. Aryl iodides, bromides, and chlorides **68** can be reduced by this method in moderate to excellent yields (Scheme 20a). Moreover, C–H arylated products **72** were obtained in moderate to good yields when carrying out the reaction in DMSO and in the presence of an excess of trapping reagents **71** (Scheme 20b). A heterogeneous catalytic system has been also reported for this kind of transformation.^{[65] [66]}

Scheme 20. The reduction and coupling reaction of aryl bromides and chlorides utilizing the con-PET process.

Operationally more convenient than the sparsely soluble perylene bisimides is rhodamine 6G **75** (Scheme 21).^[67] This xantheno dye accepts one electron from the sacrificial electron donor DIPEA under green light irradiation to form a stable radical anion in the ground state (Rh-6G^{•-}). This radical anion is colored and can absorb a second photon ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 455 \text{ nm}$), reaching the excited state (Rh-6G^{•-*}).^[68] The reduction power of the radical anion ground state (ca. -1.0 V vs. SCE) and the excited state (ca. -2.4 V vs. SCE) differ significantly, therefore, the catalysts reactivity can be tuned depending on the light color. König and coworkers took advantage of this tunability to selectively functionalize

different substrates. As an example, when 1,4-dibromo-2,5-difluorobenzene **73** or 2,4,6-tribromopyrimidine **78** were irradiated with green light, only the mono-substituted C–H arylated product **76** or **79** are obtained (Scheme 21a, left). In contrast, when the reaction mixture was irradiated with blue light, the di-substituted C–H arylated product **77** or **80**, respectively (Scheme 21a, right) is obtained. Moreover, it is possible to perform sequential C–H arylation reactions with different trapping reagents (Scheme 21b). The catalytic system was used in the synthesis of bis-heteroarenes,^[69] pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]quinolines and ullazines.^[70]

Scheme 21. Chromoselective one- or two- or sequential photoreactions.

3. Carbon – Heteroatom bond formation

In this section we discuss methods to form C-heteroatom bonds. Additional examples can be found in sections 7 and 8.

3.1 C-N bond formation

Aromatic and heteroaromatic amines are an important structural motif of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and organic materials.^[71] Therefore, the search for synthetic methods for their preparation has been a field of interest for scientists over decades. Aromatic amines are typically prepared through reduction of nitro arenes,^[72] nucleophilic aromatic substitutions,^[73] or transition metal catalyzed cross coupling reactions, such as the Buchwald-Hartwig cross coupling reaction,^[74] the Ullman coupling^[75] or the Chan-Lam reaction.^[76] More recently oxidative C–H amination methods have been reported,^[77] but they often require stoichiometric oxidants. Photoredox catalysis opens yet another door to construct the desired Csp²-N bonds.

Scheme 22. C-N bond formation.

The pioneering work of Skell^[78] demonstrated that *N*-bromophthalimide under UV-irradiation undergoes photolysis yielding a phthalimide *N*-centered radical and a bromine radical. Taking this lead, in 2014 Sanford and coworkers have reported a visible light photocatalyzed C-H amination of arenes and heteroarenes (Scheme 23).^[79] Alkyl substituted *N*-acyloxyphthalimides under reduction conditions are known to release CO₂, R•, and a phthalimide anion.^[80,81] However, by increasing the electron-withdrawing character of the *N*-substituent, this reactivity can be reversed, favoring the formation of an *N*-centered radical. Starting from the *N*-trifluoromethylacyloxyphthalimide **85** and substituted arenes and heteroarenes **86**, using the commercially available [Ir(ppy)₃] **51** as a photocatalyst, the corresponding arylated phthalimides were prepared in generally good yields, although with moderate regioselectivity. Subsequently, other sources of *N*-centered radicals for the C-H amination of arenes and heteroarenes appeared (see SI, Scheme S5).^[82, 83]

Scheme 23. A visible light photocatalyzed C-H amination of arenes and heteroarenes using *N*-acyloxyphthalimides.

König and coworkers reported the visible light mediated C-H amidation of heteroarenes **89** with benzoyl azides **88** (Scheme 24a).^[84] Azides bearing electron withdrawing and donating substituents were successfully coupled with a variety of differently *N*-substituted pyrroles and indoles. Notably, free N-H functionalities were tolerated, which might be an advantage for the late stage functionalization in organic synthesis. Furan, benzofuran or thiophene derivatives afforded the coupled products in lower yields (Scheme 24a). Later, the same group reported the visible light photocatalyzed sulfonamidation of pyrroles (Scheme 24b).^[85] The reaction proceeds smoothly with sulfonamides bearing alkyl or benzyl substituents and heteroaryl, alkyl or CF₃ groups in the sulfone, but is limited to pyrrole derivatives (Scheme 24b).

Scheme 24. The C-H amidation of heteroarenes with benzoyl azides by photosensitization.

Based on the previous reports from Fukuzumi and coworkers on the C-H oxygenation and fluorination of aromatic compounds using quinolinium derivatives as a photocatalyst,^[86] Nicewicz and coworkers reported the oxidative amination of electron rich arenes using the acridinium salt **96** as photocatalyst and catalytic amounts of TEMPO as co-catalyst (Scheme 25).^[87] Different alkoxyated arenes were successfully aminated in a highly regioselective way, following the same directing group ability of substituents known in electrophilic aromatic substitutions.

Scheme 25. The oxidative amination of electron rich arenes using acridinium salt derivatives as photocatalyst and catalytic amounts of TEMPO.

One of the key aspects of Pd-catalyzed C-N coupling methods is the design of ligands able to destabilize the Pd(II) amido complex intermediates, promoting the reductive elimination that results in the C-N bond formation.^[88] Based on this concept, Buchwald and MacMillan envisioned that electron transfer might be an alternative approach to destabilize a metal-amido complex intermediate. They reported the C-N coupling reaction between aryl halides **68** and alkyl substituted primary and secondary amines **100** using a combination of NiBr₂·glyme and [Ir] **101** with an extremely low catalyst loading (0.02 mol%) (Scheme 26a).^[89] Single electron transfer (SET) from the Ni(II)-amino complex intermediate to the photocatalyst generates a less stable Ni(III)-amino complex that undergoes reductive elimination to form **102**. Similarly, Oredinde and Johannes have reported the cross coupling reaction of primary aryl amines **103** with aryl halides **68** to obtain diarylated amines **104**. The driving force is again a SET from the photocatalyst to the amino-metal complex, ultimately generating a Ni(III) complex that undergoes reductive elimination to afford **104** (Scheme 26b).^[90] This reaction is independent of the electronic nature of the substituents present in the aryl halide or in the aryl amine. Besides aniline derivatives, 3-aminopyridine and sulfonamides also undergo the reaction. Jamison and co-workers reported an elegant regioselective synthesis of indolines.^[91] Starting from 2-haloanilines and alkenes, the combination of photoredox catalysis with nickel catalysis was determinant to avoid the β-hydride elimination (forming Heck-type products), in favor of the C-N bond reductive elimination that provides the desired indolines.

Scheme 26. Merging nickel and photoredox catalysis for C-N bond forming reactions.

Assuming that proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET) might enable the activation of N-H bonds^[94] and using the effective bond strength (bond dissociation free energy-“BDFE”) concept introduced by Mayer,^[95] Knowles described a series of C-N bond formation methods starting from anilines,^[93] amido derivatives^[96] or alkyl amines,^[97] and alkenes (see SI, Scheme S6). Leonori and coworkers have developed a photocatalytic synthesis of five-membered *N*-heterocycles from *O*-aryl oximes^[98] and, electron-poor aryloxy-amides^[99] as precursors of nitrogen-centered radicals (see SI, Scheme S7).

The α -amino carbonyl or carboxyl moiety is present in thousands of compounds with interesting biological properties and complex natural products.^[100] Many stereoselective syntheses¹ have been devised,^[101] such as catalytic α -aminations of ketones or aldehydes with electrophilic diazo-compounds,^[102] or insertion of carbenes into N-H bonds (Scheme 27).^[103] Photoredox catalysis affords here alternative methods starting from non-prefunctionalized compounds, and expanding the scope of nitrogen atom sources.

Scheme 27. The α -carbonyl amination methods.

In 2013, MacMillan and coworkers described the organocatalyzed enantioselective α -amination of aldehydes **10** via the use of amines bearing a photolabile group as the amino radical precursors.^[14] They found that dinitrophenylsulfonyloxy (ODNs) amines and carbamates **105** are the optimal amino radical precursor for coupling with the chiral enamine that is generated *in situ* between aldehyde **10** and catalyst **106** (Scheme 28).

Scheme 28. Organocatalyzed enantioselective α -amination of aldehydes.

Instead of amination of chiral enamines, Meggers and coworkers demonstrated an analogous amination of enolates, generated *in situ* from **108** and chiral rhodium complex **109**, which serves at the same time as a SET catalyst for ODNs- carbamates **105**. (Scheme 29).^[104] This way, the α -aminated product **110** was formed in good to excellent yields and enantioselectivities (Scheme 29). Electron-rich substituents decelerate the reaction rate, while sterically more bulky ODNs-carbamates **105** proved to be especially suitable coupling partners. An aromatic substituent in the α -position to the carbonyl group in **108** is required, likely due to the lower pK_a value of the α -protons.

Scheme 29. The enantioselective amination of 2-acyl imidazole derivatives using chiral Rh-catalyst.

Taking the reversed approach, i.e. coupling amines with carbon centered radicals, Peters and Fu reported a photoinduced Ullmann C-N coupling of carbazole derivatives.^{[105][106]} Coordination of copper with carbazoles generates a luminescent complex able to undergo SET to aryl or alkyl halides, which triggers the formation of C-N coupling products. Based on this process, an asymmetric α -carbonyl amination of readily available electrophilic tertiary alkyl chlorides **111** and **112** became possible through chiral copper complexes employing the phosphine ligand (*S*)-L* **113**,^[107] which not only allowed the synthesis of **114** with high enantioselectivity, but also enhanced the rate of the reaction (Scheme 30).

Scheme 30. The photoinduced Ullmann C-N coupling using copper, carbazole derivatives, and aryl halides.

3.2 C-S bond formation

The presence of C-S bonds in many molecules with pharmacological interest^[108] triggers the development of new C-S bond forming methods. The Stadler-Ziegler reaction^[109] converts aryl amines into the

REVIEW

corresponding diazonium salts, which react with thiolates to give aryl sulfides. This reaction has a broad scope and is widely applied in industry. In addition, more recent methods rely on the use of transition metal catalysis to couple thiols with aryl halides or boronic acids.^[110]

Scheme 31. C-S bond formation.

In 2013 two photocatalytic approaches for the synthesis of sulphides appeared. Jacobi von Wangelin reported a photocatalyzed synthesis of aryl methyl sulphides starting from dimethylsulfide,^[111] while Noël, Cuny, and Wang developed the photocatalytic version of the one pot Stadler-Ziegler reaction (see SI, Scheme S8).^[112]

Later, two new approaches combining metal and photoredox catalysis appeared that allowed the use of aryl halides as coupling partners instead. Johannes and Oderinde developed a cross coupling reaction of thiols **115** with aryl and heteroaryl iodides **68-I** (Scheme 32a).^[113] Photo-generated thiol radicals, experimentally confirmed by trapping with olefin **118** (Scheme 32b), are proposed to enter into the nickel catalytic cycle to yield the desired thioethers. The scope of the aryl iodides is very broad, and a large variety of functional groups can be used for orthogonal transformations. The method is effective for aromatic or alkylic thiols. At the same time, Molander and coworkers reported the thioetherification of aryl and heteroaryl bromides with thio-silicates (Scheme 32c).^[114] A variety of electron rich and electron neutral aryl and heteroaryl bromides **68-Br** were successfully coupled, but the coupling of electron rich bromides was not observed. The limited availability of thiol-substituted silanes **120** prompted then the development of a three-component reaction (Scheme 32d), that allowed the coupling of a variety of alkyl thiols bearing sensitive functional groups such as free amines or alcohols, ketones, or amino acid derivatives.

Scheme 32. The photocatalyzed C-S bond formation.

In addition, a photoredox catalyzed radical thiol-ene reaction was described by Yoon.^[115] Direct oxidation of thiols **124** by the excited [Ru(bpz)₃(PF₆)₂]* generate a thiyl radical that adds to **125** with anti-Markovnikov selectivity (Scheme 33). A variety of dialkyl thioethers were synthesized in good yields.

Scheme 33. Photoredox catalyzed radical thiol-ene reaction.

Vinyl sulfones are important building blocks employed as intermediates or starting materials in a large number of transformations.^[116] Most of them exhibit interesting biological properties, for example as inhibitors of enzymes such as cysteine proteases,^[117] sortases,^[118] or protein tyrosine phosphatases.^[119] The synthesis of vinyl sulfones includes conventional Knoevenagel condensation^[120] or the Horner-Emmons reaction.^[121] Moreover, transition metal catalyzed approaches between alkenes or alkynes with sodium sulfonates,^[122] and alkynes with sulfonic acids are effective.^[123] At this point, visible light photocatalysis offer an alternative approach based on the oxidation of sulfonates, using an organic dye as catalyst of the reaction.

Scheme 34. Synthesis of vinyl-sulfones.

König and coworkers reported that Eosin Y under green light irradiation is able to photooxidize arylsulfonates **128**, that couples with cyclic and acyclic alkenes **129** to yield vinyl sulfones **130**.^[124] Same radical intermediates are generated in the photoreduction of sulfonyl chlorides (see ATRA section 7.3.2). The radical pathway of the reaction was supported by the detection of the TEMPO-adduct **131** (Scheme 35a). In a second report, they extended the scope of the reaction to primary and secondary alkyl substituted and heteroaryl substituted sulfones, with good results (Scheme 35b).^[125] Employing a similar photocatalytic system, Wang developed a difunctionalization of alkynes (see SI, Scheme 9).^[126]

Scheme 35. The visible light mediated organo-photoredox catalyzed synthesis of vinyl sulfones from aryl sulfonates and alkenes.

Aromatic sulfoxide moieties can be found in natural products,^[127] herbicides,^[128] drugs^[129] and performance materials.^[130] Consequently, several routes have been described for their synthesis, including oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides,^[131] or the nucleophilic substitution of sulfinyl derivatives with organomagnesium reagents (Scheme 36).^[132] Moreover, several electrophilic aromatic substitution reactions were also reported, for example, the aluminium chloride catalyzed arene sulfonylation of benzene or toluene with sulfinyl chlorides,^[133] or the Friedel-Crafts type reaction of methylsulfonates with electron rich aromatic compounds using stoichiometric aluminium chloride.^[134] Another approach involves the palladium catalyzed arylation of sulfenate ions with aryl triflates and halides.^[135] In comparison to the large amount of methods available in traditional chemistry, photocatalysis has less to offer, because to date, only one method has been reported so far.

Scheme 36. Synthesis of sulfoxides.

The visible light accelerated C-H sulfonylation of heteroarenes starts from bench stable, easy to handle and commercially available sulfinamides **132** and electron-rich aromatic compounds **133**, using persulfate as the stoichiometric oxidant (Scheme 37).^[136] The reaction gave moderate to good yields with *N*-butyl-arylsulfonamides bearing electron donating or withdrawing substituents, while the presence of electron donating substituents in the aromatic or heteroaromatic partner afforded excellent results. However, the reaction only took place with electron rich aromatic and heteroaromatic compounds, thus pointing to an electrophilic Friedel-Craft-type reaction mechanism.

Scheme 37. The visible light accelerated C-H sulfonylation of heteroarenes.

3.3 C-O bond formation

Aryl ethers are traditionally synthesized through transition metal catalyzed cross coupling of aryl halides and alcohols. A classic example is the copper-mediated Ullmann reaction,^[137] some of whose drawbacks, such as a large amount of alkoxide required or the limited scope in the alcohols, have been overcome over the years by improving the efficiency of the catalytic system using different ligands.^[138] In addition, many palladium catalyzed approaches have been reported, providing the desired compounds with excellent results.^[139]

Scheme 38. C-O bond formation.

Hillhouse and coworkers reported that Ni(II) alkoxide complexes do not undergo reductive elimination, and conversion to the corresponding less stable Ni(III) alkoxides is required to initiate the elimination.^[140] MacMillan and coworkers have demonstrated that the use of photoredox catalysis may facilitate the oxidation of Ni(II) complex intermediates to Ni(III) favoring the reductive elimination step, and overcoming the previously reported drawback.^[141] Using NiCl₂, and the [Ir] **101**, an array of aryl bromides **68** bearing electron-withdrawing or electron-donating substituents were successfully coupled with primary and secondary alcohols **135**, showing that the electronic nature of the substituents present in the aryl halide does not affect the reactivity (Scheme 39a). The same group developed a unique cross coupling reaction between carboxylic acids and aryl bromides for the synthesis of *O*-aryl esters **138** that could not be carried out so far under thermal conditions (Scheme 39b).^[142] Using NiBr₂-diglyme (5 mol%) and Ir(ppy)₃ (2 mol%) as photosensitizer under visible light irradiation, a variety of aromatic compounds could be coupled with alkyl and aryl carboxylic acids **137**, giving rise to the corresponding esters **138** in good yields. The authors propose that the Ir(III) acts as an antenna absorbing visible light. Energy transfer from the excited Ir(III)* to a Ni(II) complex (bearing the carboxylate and the arene) affords an excited Ni(II)* with the appropriate electronic structure to undergo reductive elimination (not feasible under thermal conditions), yielding the desired aryl esters in good yields. Efficient ISC and a larger extinction co-efficient of the Ir complex compared to the Ni complex define its role in the photo-metal catalysis.

Scheme 39. Dual Ni(II)- and photocatalytic approach for C-O bond formation.

3.4 C-P bond formation

Organophosphorus compounds are commonly prepared by transition metal catalyzed cross coupling reactions of $\text{R}_2\text{P(O)H}$ via P-H bond activation.^[143] Palladium-catalyzed approaches are well established and a variety of aryl precursors can be used, such as halides,^[144] boronic acids,^[145] triflates,^[146] or sulfonates.^[147] In addition, copper and nickel catalyzed approaches were also developed with good results,^[148] but the reaction conditions required and in some cases, the limited scope, call for the development of new methods. Few methods have been developed in the field of photoredox catalysts that work at room temperature, and in some cases, avoid the use of transition metals.

Scheme 40. C-P bond formation.

Kobayashi reported the hydrophosphorylation of unactivated alkenes, where the key intermediate is a P-centered radical formed by reductive quenching of the photoexcited rhodamine B with diarylphosphine oxide.^[149] Based on this report, Xiao and coworkers developed a cross-coupling reaction between diarylphosphine oxides **139** and aryl iodides **68-I** by merging nickel catalysis and photoredox catalysis (Scheme 41).^[150] Reductive quenching of the photoexcited Ru(II)* photocatalyst by the diarylphosphine oxide yields a P-centered radical, that entered the metal catalytic cycle to afford the desired triarylphosphine oxides **140**. Electron-donating and slightly electron-withdrawing groups in the aryl iodides are well tolerated, as well as the sterically hindered 1-iodonaphthalene. The reaction works well with ditolylphosphine oxide, but electron rich secondary phosphine oxides, such as dialkylated ones, did not give the desired product.

Scheme 41. Cross coupling of diarylphosphine oxides and aryl iodides merging nickel catalysis and photoredox catalysis

Later on, Toste and coworkers reported the gold-catalyzed oxidative P-arylation of H-phosphonates **141** mediated by visible light photoredox catalysis.^[151] A combination of 10 mol% Ph_3PAuCl and 2 mol% $[\text{Ru}]$ **40** in a mixture of MeCN/EtOH (4/1) under visible light irradiation afforded a variety of aryl phosphonates **142** in good yields (Scheme 42a). The reaction could also be carried out with an *in situ* generated diazonium salt synthesized from the corresponding aniline (Scheme 42b).

Scheme 42. The gold-catalyzed oxidative P-arylation of H-phosphonates mediated by visible light photoredox catalysis.

König and coworkers have developed two new phosphonilation methods following a reductive^[152] or an oxidative^[153] pathway respectively that allows the phosphonilation of compounds with different electronic properties (see SI, Scheme S10)

3.5 C-Cl bond formation

Chlorinated aromatic compounds are important synthetic intermediates in organic synthesis.^[154] Traditionally, chlorination of aromatic compounds is carried out by electrophilic substitution using either chlorine gas or highly reactive reagents such as SO_2Cl_2 or $t\text{-BuOCl}$, which often found to be less selective.^[155] Moreover, the chlorination can be carried out by using *N*-chloro precursors, such as *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS) or *N*-chloroamines that present moderate reactivity and requires additional activation with active metals, Lewis acids or Brønsted acids.^[156]

Alternatively, König, Wolf, and coworkers^[157] have developed a biomimetic chlorination reaction of aromatic compounds based on the mechanism of action of flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD)-dependent halogenases.^[158] Riboflavin tetraacetate (RFT) **148** is used as the catalytic system, replacing the FAD and NADH_2 biomolecules. They observed that acetic acid is necessary for the reaction to take place, because the peracetic acid (AcOOH), formed in the media is responsible for the formation of the "Cl⁺" synthons that undergo electrophilic aromatic substitution reaction, affording the chlorinated products. A variety of electron rich arenes were chlorinated using RFT and HCl under blue light irradiation (Scheme 43). Different aniline and anisole

REVIEW

derivatives **147** were successfully chlorinated in good to excellent yields, although low regioselectivity in many cases. Substrates bearing two electron donating substituents define the scope of the method, because their undesired direct oxidation by the photocatalyst decreases the yield of the reaction. The reaction was also applied to the α -chlorination of acetophenones **146** with good results (Scheme 43).

Scheme 43. A biomimetic chlorination reaction of aromatic compounds.

4. α -Amine functionalization

Tertiary amines are often used as sacrificial electron donor in reductive photocatalytic cycles, making use of their facile oxidation to an N-centered radical cation. Such intermediates can lose a hydrogen atom or a proton from an adjacent α -carbon, resulting either in electrophilic iminium cations that can be trapped by nucleophiles or in α -amino radicals that can undergo coupling with electrophiles. Based on these two principles, many photoredox catalytic methods for the formation of C-C bonds alpha to an amine were developed.^[159]

4.1. Via iminium ion intermediates

The most common non-photocatalytic method to functionalize the α -position to an amine through iminium ion formation is the cross-dehydrogenative coupling (CDC).^[160] Commonly, Cu(I) salts are used as a catalyst in combination with a stoichiometric oxidant, such as TBHP (Scheme 44). In contrast, photocatalytic systems allow the use of molecular oxygen as the terminal oxidant.

Scheme 44. α -Amine functionalization.

In 2010 Stephenson and coworkers reported the formation of iminium ion intermediates **153** from tertiary amines **151** under photocatalytic conditions (Scheme 45).^[161] Nitroalkanes proved to be suitable trapping reagents for this intermediates, affording **152** in high yields under mild conditions.

Scheme 45. The visible light photocatalyzed aza-Henry reaction.

Using eosin Y as a photocatalyst, König and coworkers reported the generation of the iminium ion **153** and expanded the scope of the reaction (Scheme 46).^[162] Malonates **154** and dialkyl phosphonates **158** afforded the corresponding β -diester amines **155** and α -amino phosphonates **159** in good to excellent yields. The use of malononitrile **156** as the pro-nucleophile afforded α -amino nitriles **157** (Scheme 46a), being precursors of α -amino acids, aldehydes or alcohols. Furthermore, Rueping and coworkers successfully developed a dual catalytic system for the α -alkynylation of tetrahydroisoquinolines **151** using [Ru(bpy)₂(dtbbpy)](PF₆)₂ **161** as the photocatalyst able to form the iminium ion, and a copper complex as the co-catalyst able to activate a terminal acetylene (Scheme 46b).^[163] The exact same transformation was previously reported by Li and coworkers using CuBr/TBHP as the catalytic system requiring a reaction temperature of 100 °C, which afforded **162** in good yields (58-82 %) in a shorter time (3 h).^[164]

Scheme 46. Visible light induced α -alkylations and α -alkynylations of tetrahydroisoquinolines.

Independently Li^[165] and Rueping^[166] reported the α -arylation of α -amino carbonyl compounds using a transition metal photocatalysts (Scheme 47). In the case of Rueping, a Lewis acid (zinc acetate as a cocatalyst) was used to activate the aminocarbonyl compound **163** (Scheme 47). In both reports, the arylated compounds **164** were obtained in moderate to good yields.

Scheme 47. The α -arylation of α -amino carbonyl compounds using a transition metal photocatalysts.

The combination of visible light photoredox catalysis and organocatalysis allowed the synthesis of β -aminoketones,^[167] β -aminoesters^[168] and α -aminoketones^[169] (See SI, Scheme S11).

4.2. Via α -amino radical intermediates:

REVIEW

α -Amino radicals are another class of intermediates that can be generated from amine radical cations, but unlike iminium ions, they are nucleophilic species. Although less exploited than the chemistry of iminium ions, several photoredox catalyzed reactions have been recently reported in this area. These reactions are conducted under inert gas conditions, unlike the iminium ion formation that in general require air or oxygen, and do not call for the presence of a stoichiometric external oxidant, because of the redox-neutral nature of the reaction (Scheme 48 right).

Probably, one of the oldest approaches for generating nucleophilic α -amino carbon centers is the α -lithiation of amines, which can be reacted with electrophiles.^[170] Due to the high reactivity of such organolithium species, transmetalation with copper or zinc has proven to be a valuable strategy to extend the scope of such processes (Scheme 48 left). Switching from ionic to radical chemistry in photocatalysis, allowed the development of milder reaction condition methods.

Scheme 48. Generation and trapping of α -amino centered radicals.

MacMillan and coworkers have described a direct arylation of α -amino C-H bonds with cyanoarenes **166** as the coupling partner.^[171] Initial reduction of the cyanoarene with the Ir(III) catalyst **51** generates a radical anion intermediate. In turn, oxidation of the amine with the oxidized Ir(IV) species yields an amine radical cation, which after deprotonation with a soft base affords the α -amino radical. Coupling of these intermediates with concurrent cyanide elimination yields α -arylated amines **167** in good to excellent yields. The reaction was mainly applied to heterocyclic amines and cyanoarenes bearing electron-withdrawing substituents (Scheme 49).

Scheme 49. Visible-light enabled direct arylation of α -amino C-H bonds with cyanoarenes.

In short succession, a number of reports appeared that successfully described the reaction of photochemically generated α -amino radicals with α,β -unsaturated alkenes. Beginning with the report by Reiser and coworkers in 2012 (Scheme 50a),^[172] detailing the synthesis of adducts **169**, in which an α -amino radical intermediate derived from **151** was made plausible by isolation either of the self-dimerization product **170** or, in the presence of air, of the amide **171**. Later on, Yoon reported that Brønsted acids as co-catalyst significantly improved the efficiency of the reaction, allowing the activation of the electrophile **172** by protonation without shutting down the initial oxidation of the amine (Scheme 50b).^[173]

Scheme 50. The visible light photocatalyzed α -amino radical addition to Michael acceptors.

Other non-heterocyclic amines were also functionalized using this method. Nishibayashi and coworkers reported the addition of α -amino radicals of aniline derivatives to Michael acceptors bearing two electron withdrawing groups (Scheme 51a, top).^[174] They showed that the use of Ir(III) complexes as catalyst and the choice of the solvent is critical for the outcome of the reaction. Using **177** as a radical clock in the coupling with **178**, the product **179** was exclusively obtained, again proving the radical nature of the process (Scheme 51a, bottom). Rueping and coworkers reported an insightful variant of this theme, demonstrating the effect of oxygen on the outcome of the coupling between **180** and **181**.^[175] Oxidation of anilines with an Ir(III) catalyst under argon atmosphere in the presence of Michael acceptors gave the 1,4-addition products **183** (Scheme 51b, left), while in presence of air, an addition/cyclization reaction takes place affording tetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives **184** (Scheme 51b right). The two reactions diverge in the reactivity of the intermediate **182**. Under argon atmosphere the radical undergoes one electron reduction by Ir(II), generating an anion that is protonated. Alternatively, intermediate **182** can undergo intramolecular radical arylation to form a cyclohexadienyl radical, which in the absence of oxygen is a reversible process. However, in the presence of oxygen, Ir(II) is oxidized to Ir(III) and superoxide forms, which accepts an electron and a proton from the cyclohexadienyl radical affording products **184**.

Scheme 51. The visible light photocatalyzed α -amino radical addition to Michael acceptors.

REVIEW

4.3 Formation of α -amino centered radicals via 1,6-*H* atom translocation (HAT):

In 2002, Parsons and coworkers pioneered a *n*-Bu₃SnH/AIBN mediated strategy for the generation of α -amino radicals via 1,6-*H* atom translocation (HAT) from adjacent vinyl radicals for the synthesis of the tricyclic mitomycin ring system.^[176] Following this protocol, in 2008, Reiser and coworkers extended the scope of this transformation to the synthesis of useful indoline derivatives **186** from the corresponding α -bromocinnamate derivatives **185** (Scheme 52, left).^[177] A complementary method starting from *ortho*-amino- α -bromocinnamates **185** was developed utilizing visible light photoredox catalysis (Scheme 52, right).^[178] The latter protocol requires very low catalyst loading (0.3 mol%) at room temperature (Scheme 52), comparing favourably to the former, which calls for high-temperature conditions and stoichiometric use of Bu₃SnH. It is proposed that the generation of the vinyl radical **185a** occurs by the extrusion of a bromide anion triggered by an SET from the Ir(III) catalyst in a reductive quenching cycle, followed by 1,6-HAT process giving the α -amino radical **185b**, which rapidly undergoes 5-*exo-trig* cyclization to the desired product (Scheme 52).

Scheme 52. Synthesis of indolines by *n*-Bu₃SnH/AIBN and visible light photocatalytic method.

5. Decarboxylative coupling reactions

Carboxylic acids are important structures broadly employed in organic synthesis. Their high stability, low toxicity, easy availability and low price make them perfect substrates to be used as starting material for many reactions. Since the 1930s, when Hunsdiecker and coworkers discovered that in the presence of dry silver salts aromatic carboxylic acids can undergo oxidative decarboxylation,^[179] many methods involving C-C bond formation have been reported.

5.1. Alkyl radicals via photocatalytic decarboxylation

Decarboxylation of aliphatic acids or activated esters result in highly reactive alkyl radicals that can be utilized for the formation of new C-C bonds. Under non-photocatalytic conditions, the decarboxylation of *N*-hydroxyphthalimide esters has been carried out with stoichiometric Zn reagents and Ni(II) catalysts to perform the cross-coupling step.^[180] Photocatalytic methods allow the decarboxylation of protected and non-protected acids, and not always require the presence of a second catalyst to perform the cross coupling.

Scheme 53. Decarboxylative coupling reactions

5.1.1 Decarboxylation of carboxylic acids

In 2013, Nishibayashi utilized the excited Ir(III) catalyst **189** for the visible light mediated, oxidative decarboxylation of *p*-amino substituted arylacetic acids **187**, resulting in benzyl radicals, which can be trapped with electron deficient olefins (Scheme 54).^[181]

Scheme 54. A visible light-mediated photocatalyzed decarboxylative coupling of arylacetic acids and electron deficient olefins.

Switching to the iridium catalyst **192**, MacMillan and coworkers achieved the arylation by decarboxylation of α -amino acids **191**, especially relevant for pharmaceutical applications (Scheme 55).^[182] Additionally, α -alkoxy and α -amino acids were decarboxylated and coupled with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds^[183] or with vinyl sulfones giving rise to α -vinylated adducts.^[184] The scope was then extended to electron rich arenes,^[185] vinyl-^[186] and alkyl halides,^[187] and the functionalization of aryl triflates (See SI, Scheme S12 and S13).^[188]

Scheme 55. The photocatalyzed arylation of α -amino acids with cyanoarenes.

Next to Ni-catalysts, palladium can also be employed as cocatalyst in photocatalytic reactions. Taking the lead from Tsuji-Trost allylations, Tunge and coworkers demonstrated that Pd-allyl complexes undergo coupling with benzyl radicals generated by photocatalyzed decarboxylation (Scheme 56).^[189] The mild reaction conditions and no requirement of additional activating reagents compare well to classic palladium-catalyzed benzylic allylation processes.^[190]

Scheme 56. The decarboxylative allylation of amino alkanolic acids.

5.1.2 Decarboxylation of derivatives of carboxylic acids

REVIEW

Apart from carboxylic acids, acid derivatives can also be activated for radical decarboxylation reactions. After the first report from Oda and Okada in 1991,^[180] in which they described the visible light induced decarboxylative fragmentation of acyloxyphtalimides, Overmann and coworkers elegantly applied this method for the synthesis of (-)-Aplyvioline, achieving as a key step the fragment coupling between **197** and **198** with good yields and excellent stereoselectivity (Scheme 57a).^[191] Another application was reported by Reiser and coworkers with the synthesis of (spiro)annelated butenolides **201** starting from readily available furanes derivatives **200**.^[192] An energy transfer from Ir (III)* to **200** followed by intramolecular electron transfer is proposed that triggers the N-O fragmentation. Consecutive decarboxylation generates an alkyl radical that undergoes cyclization to afford the spiro-compounds **201** (Scheme 57b).

Scheme 57. Decarboxylation of N-hydroxyphthalimide esters as key step for natural product synthesis.

Recently, König and coworkers have reported the first metal-free photocatalyzed decarboxylative alkylation reaction.^[193] Starting from *N*-(acyloxy)-phtalimines **202**, the reaction gave good results with a broad spectrum of α -amino or α -oxy acids and fatty acids, as well as with a large variety of electron deficient olefins (Scheme 58). Determination of TEMPO-**204** by LC-MS confirmed the presence of radical intermediates, while a quantum yield of $\Phi = 2.6 \pm 0.5\%$ suggested that radical chains are unlikely in this mechanism.

Scheme 58. Metal-free photocatalyzed decarboxylative alkylation reactions.

5.2 Acyl radicals via photocatalytic decarboxylation

Ketoacids are important acylating agents broadly utilized in different transformations to deliver a carbonyl group *via* decarboxylative coupling to arenes, alkenes, or even alkanes.^[194] Moreover, the

combination of metal and photoredox catalysis allows to extend the scope of organic molecules that can be acylated.

Scheme 59. Generation and trapping of acyl radicals.

In 2013, Lei and Lan developed the first visible light mediated photoredox catalyzed decarboxylative amidation of α -ketoacids **205** (Scheme 60).^[195] The authors propose that a superoxide radical anion is formed and responsible for the formation of the acyl radical by oxidation of the carboxylate followed by decarboxylation, that is trapped by the amine, yielding amides **207** in moderate to excellent yields (Scheme 60). The reaction gives good results with electron-rich aryl and heteroaryl substituents in the α -ketoacid and electron-rich aryl or alkyl substituents in the amine, but the use of starting materials bearing electron withdrawing substituent was not reported.

Scheme 60. The visible light mediated photoredox catalyzed decarboxylative amidation of α -ketoacids.

After this first example, many other acylation reactions were reported. As an example, Fu and co-workers were able to couple acyl radicals **205** with Michael acceptors **208**, for the synthesis of difunctional compounds **210** (Scheme 61).^[196] After a screening of photocatalysts in the reaction, they observed that the excited state lifetime together with the oxidative potential of the photocatalyst seems to be crucial for the reaction to take place in an effective way, as well as the presence of a base. The reaction is compatible with electron rich aromatic or heteroaromatic substituents in the α -ketoacid, and with a large variety of Michael acceptors, such as α,β -unsaturated ketones, esters or amides, or vinyl sulfones and acrylonitrile. Radical trapping experiments with TEMPO afforded **211** in 91% yield, thus confirming the radical decarboxylative pathway of the reaction.

Scheme 61. The synthesis of γ -carbonylic compounds via acyl radical.

Also here the combination of metal and photoredox catalysis has expanded the number of currently available transformations. MacMillan and coworkers reported a decarboxylative arylation of α -ketoacids using [Ir] **101** as photocatalyst and Ni(II)-catalyst (Scheme 62a).^[197] Aryl and heteroaryl bromides or iodides bearing electron donor or acceptor substituents are well tolerated in the reaction, as well as primary or secondary alkyl substituents or electron rich arenes in the ketoacids

REVIEW

(Scheme 62a). In this line of transformations, they demonstrated that anhydrides **215** (formed *in situ* from acyl chlorides **214** and acids **213** in presence of DBU), can undergo metal insertion–decarboxylation–recombination when subjected to metallophotoredox catalysis (Scheme 62b).^[198] Ni(0) undergoes oxidative insertion in the O-COR bond of the anhydrides **215**, forming an acyl carboxylate Ni(II) complex that is oxidized by the excited Ir(III), inducing oxidative decarboxylation. Final reductive elimination affords the desired ketones **216** in moderate to good yields. The reaction was examined with a large variety of α -amino acids and alkyl or aryl substituted acyl chlorides. Subsequently, Doyle and co-workers reported the α -acylation of amines using acyl chlorides or anhydrides and dual metallophotoredox catalysis.^[199]

Scheme 62. A decarboxylative arylation of α -ketoacids using Ir(III)-photocatalyst and Ni(II)-catalyst.

6 Cycloadditions

Cycloadditions continue to be one of the most powerful methods to rapidly assemble complex molecules in a stereoselective way.^[200] The Woodward-Hoffmann rules provide an edifice for these reactions, defining by HOMO/LUMO orbital symmetry and its energy gap the course of the transformation with respect to reactivity and selectivity.^[201] Orbital symmetry considerations dictate if a concerted cycloaddition can proceed thermally or photochemically, and the latter reaction mode needs to be chosen for $4n$ π -electron systems, notably in [2+2]-cycloadditions.^[202,203] Here the reaction proceeds between one ground state and one excited state molecule (SOMO/LUMO interaction) to allow a geometrically favored, suprafacial approach of the reactants. Nevertheless, even if a cycloaddition is possible based on orbital symmetry considerations, it might still not proceed because of a too large HOMO/LUMO energy gap. Lewis acid or organocatalysis can overcome this obstacle, typically by lowering the LUMO in energy.^[204,205]

6.1 [4+2]-Cycloadditions (Diels-Alder reactions)

Another possibility to close the HOMO/LUMO gap in a [4+2]-cycloaddition is to oxidize the diene or dienophile to a radical cation, this way both lowering their HOMO and LUMO without changing the symmetry of the interacting orbitals in the reaction. This area has been widely developed over the decades,^[206] since via this Umpolung approach the substrate scope for cycloadditions is significantly broadened and thus opening up new avenues in synthetic chemistry. A typical case is shown with the cycloaddition between isoprene **217** and styrene **218** (Scheme 63). Even under forcing conditions (200 °C, 24 h) no reaction takes place.

Scheme 63. A selected example of a Diels-Alder reaction initiated by chemical or photocatalytic one-electron oxidation.

However, in the presence of $(p\text{-Br-C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{N}^+/\text{SbCl}_6^-$ a single Diels-Alder adduct **219** is obtained in 22% yield, which was attributed to an initial oxidation of **218** to the corresponding radical cation.^[207] For proof of concept, 2,6- $(t\text{-Bu})_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_3\text{N}$ was added to rule out Brønsted acid catalysis that might occur by releasing HCl under the reaction conditions. The initial oxidation could be achieved more efficiently by a photochemical pathway; using either chromium **220**^[208] or ruthenium **221**^[209] based photocatalysts, the desired [4+2] adduct **219** were obtained in excellent yields and high catalyst turnover.

6.2 [3+2]-Cycloadditions

[3+2]-cycloadditions,^[210–212] also known as 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions, have a broad scope, typically used for the synthesis of five-membered heterocyclic rings.^[213]

6.2.1 Synthesis of pyrrole derivatives

Polysubstituted pyrrole derivatives find applications in organic synthesis and in medicinal chemistry,^[214] and consequently, many efforts have been made to develop efficient syntheses for this compound class over the decades.^[215] The [3+2]-cycloaddition of acetylene derivatives such as **223** (DMAD = dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate) and **222** provides a powerful, high-yielding entry into this class of heterocycles. The respective azomethine ylides can be generated *in situ* by the reaction of α -silylimidate **222** and phenyltrifluorosilane (Scheme 64, left)^[216] or from aldehydes **225** and benzotriazole **226**, ultimately requiring the employment of *n*-BuLi at -78 °C (Scheme 64, right).^[217] Recently, Xiao and co-workers disclosed an operationally attractive alternative (Scheme 64, bottom)^[218] by the photooxidation of 2H-aziridines **227** with Fukuzumi's catalyst **94** under blue light irradiation. The resulting radical cation **227a/227b** reacts with a variety of acetylenes **223** yielding pyrroles **224** in up to quantitative yields.

REVIEW

Scheme 64. Synthesis of pyrrole derivatives by conventional and photocatalytic methods.

6.2.2 Synthesis of pyrazole derivatives

Pyrazoles find application in the synthesis of agrochemicals^[219] and pharmaceuticals.^[220] Among the numerous approaches established over the years for their synthesis,^[221] the Cu-catalyzed [3+2] cycloaddition (Scheme 65a, top)^[222] between acetylenes **223** and arylhydrazones **228** is particularly attractive.^[223] A complementary approach, utilizing simple hydrazines **230** and readily available Michael acceptors **231** to assemble pyrazoles was recently disclosed (Scheme 65b, bottom).^[224] Under irradiation in the presence of photocatalyst **13**, the aerobic oxidation of **230** to diazene **230a** is achieved, which undergoes an annulation reaction with **231**.

Scheme 65. Synthesis of pyrazole derivatives by conventional (a) and photocatalytic (b) methods.

6.2.3 Click Reactions:

Apart from conventional [3+2]-cycloadditions,^[210–212] click reactions^[225] that proceed under mild conditions with high functional group tolerance were found to be particularly valuable.^[226] The copper(I)-catalyzed azide-alkyne [3+2] cycloaddition has become one of the most powerful ligation methods to connect two entities via a 1,4-triazole moiety.^[227] While homogeneous or heterogeneous Cu(I)-catalysts (Scheme 66)^[228] can be employed directly for this transformation, a robust and convenient protocol relies on the *in situ* reductions of CuSO₄ by ascorbic acid derivatives (Scheme 66).^[229] This activation mode can be also achieved by visible light photocatalysis utilizing flavine^[230] or the bimetallic Ru/Mn complex **237**, which in the presence of the sacrificial electron donor (triethylamine, NEt₃) can efficiently transfer an electron to Cu(II)-sulfate to generate the catalytically active Cu(I)-species (Scheme 66d, right).^[231]

Scheme 66. Non-photocatalytic (a, b, c) and photocatalytic (d) [3+2]-cycloadditions.

6.4 [2+2]-Cycloadditions

Thermal [2+2]-cycloadditions are generally not possible following a concerted pathway since this would require the antarafacial orientation between the two alkenes being geometrically difficult.^[232] An exception is [2+2]-cycloadditions of ketenes,^[233] owing to the additional π -orbital of its carbonyl group that is involved in the transition state. Formal [2+2]-cycloadditions catalyzed by soft Lewis acids that can activate carbon-carbon π -bonds have been recently disclosed by the group of Chirik.^[234] Employing iron(0)-complexes **240** bearing labile nitrogen ligands, unactivated olefins **238** and **239** are efficiently transformed to the corresponding cyclobutanes **242** with high diastereoselectivity (Scheme 67a, top). Thermal [2+2]-cycloadditions via charge transfer complexes followed by electron transfer between electron rich and electron poor alkenes, notably tetracyanoethylene being an exceptionally strong electron acceptor, are also possible.^[235]

In contrast, there are numerous examples known in the literature for photochemical [2+2]-cycloaddition under UV-irradiation, and especially the Paterno-Büchi reaction between electron-rich alkenes and carbonyl compounds has found wide applications.^[236] Pioneering work by Pandey^[237] and Yoon^[202,204,238] demonstrated that [2+2]-cycloadditions between two electron deficient alkenes can be efficiently mediated by visible light^[239] using a photoredox catalyst that is able to transfer an electron to the first alkene, thus generating a nucleophilic radical anion that couples with the second alkene by via a conjugate addition. Enantioselective variants employing chiral Lewis acids have been also reported,^[240] which allowed the synthesis of cyclobutanes with high diastereo- and enantioselectivity. As the ultimate achievement, the Yoon group was also able to fine tune this transformation in a way that only the enone activated by the chiral Lewis acid will accept an electron from a photoredox catalyst, thus avoiding background reactions, which allow the lowering of the amount of the chiral Lewis acid that must be added.^[241]

Alternatively, [2+2] cycloadditions can be achieved by energy transfer (sensitization; Scheme 1d) process,^[242] which again has ample precedent for processes under UV irradiation using sensitizers such as benzophenones.^[243] Visible light absorbing iridium complexes such as [Ir(ppy)₂(dtb-bpy)]PF₆, [Ir(dF(CF₃)ppy)₂(dtb-bpy)]PF₆ etc. can also efficiently promote [2+2]-cycloadditions by energy transfer,^[192,244] which also makes [2+2]-processes with styrenes **249** particularly effective (Scheme 68).^[245]

REVIEW

photoredox cycle (Scheme 70, right) is operating, although a competing radical chain pathway cannot be unambiguously ruled out.^[257]

Scheme 70. Selected examples for comparison of ruthenium catalysis in ATRA reaction.

7.1.2 Copper-catalyzed ATRA reactions: Direct addition of RX to alkenes

Copper-catalyzed ATRA reactions constitute an economically attractive alternative to the ruthenium- or iridium-based processes discussed above, but also offers additional features based on the ability of Cu(II) to stabilize ligands and especially radical intermediates.^[251] Perez and coworkers showed that $Tp^*Cu(NCMe)$ **257** bearing an electron rich borohydride ligand catalyzes ATRA reactions between various olefins and organic halides under thermal conditions without the need for further additives (Scheme 71, left).^[258]

Scheme 71. Selected examples for comparison of copper catalysis in ATRA reaction.

Back in 1980, Mitani and coworkers reported the CuCl-catalyzed addition of halo- or perhaloalkanes to olefins under UV-light irradiation (Scheme 72, left).^[259] A visible light-mediated alternative was reported by Reiser and coworkers^[260] making use of the Cu(I)-phenanthroline complex $[Cu(dap)_2]Cl$ **258** (Scheme 72 right).^[261] Besides homoleptic Cu(I) complexes, also heteroleptic copper(I) complexes can be readily accessed, and it was especially shown that phenanthroline / bis-isonitrile (Scheme 72, right)^[262] based catalysts are superior with respect to

reductive power and excited state lifetime ($Cu(I)^*$ ($E_{1/2} = -1.43$ V for $[Cu(dap)_2]Cl$ **258**, $\tau = 270$ ns, $E_{1/2} = -1.88$ V for $[Cu(dpp)(binc)BF_4]$ **259**, $\tau = 17$ ns) ($dpp = 2,9\text{-diphenyl-}1,10\text{-phenanthroline}$, $binc = bis(2\text{-isocyanophenyl})$ phenylphosphonate). Using these catalysts, perhaloalkanes and α -carbonyl halides (Scheme 72, right), but also electron poor benzyl halides^[263] can be coupled with alkenes (Scheme 72, right). Moreover, it was possible to use allylstannanes and allylsilanes as alkene counterparts, thus allylations of alkyl halides become possible.^[260,262]

Scheme 72. Selected examples of copper-catalyzed ATRA with UV and visible light.

As discussed for Ru(II) or Ir(III) (Scheme 82), the visible light mediated ATRA processes catalyzed by Cu(I) might follow both a photoredox cycle along with a radical chain pathway, the latter was for example proposed to operate exclusively for the copper(I)-photocatalyzed azidation of toluenes.^[264] However, the different behavior between Ru(II)- and Cu(I)-catalysts in the ATRA reaction between trifluoromethylsulfonylchloride **260** and alkenes **261** suggest the involvement of copper in the catalytic cycle beyond acting solely as an electron transfer reagent or as a radical initiator (Scheme 73). The copper(II) species formed after electron transfer from Cu(I) might stabilize and transfer ligands such as SO_2Cl^- to the radical intermediates **265**. Alternatively, Cu(II) might also take the role as a persistent radical, which might undergo a coupling with **265** to form an organocopper(III) intermediate **266**, which then closes the catalytic cycle by a reductive elimination to give rise to **263** with concurrent regeneration of the Cu(I) photocatalyst (Scheme 73).^[265,266]

REVIEW

Scheme 73. Visible light Ru(II)-catalyzed trifluoromethylchlorination vs. Cu(I)-catalyzed trifluoromethylchlorosulfonylation.

7.2 ATRA followed by elimination - synthesis of olefins

Alkenes represent arguably one of the most important classes in organic synthesis, and consequently, a great number of methods are known, among them palladium-catalyzed cross coupling reactions,^[267] Wittig reaction,^[268] or cross metathesis,^[269] etc. (Scheme 74), for which Nobel prizes were awarded.

ATRA products of type **253** (Scheme 69) can serve as direct precursors to alkenes via elimination reactions, e.g. by base induced dehydrohalogenation.^[270] Combining the latter with the photochemical ATRA step, it is also possible to directly synthesize alkenes achieving overall a sp^2 - sp^2 or sp^3 - sp^2 cross coupling.

Scheme 74. Typical methods for olefin synthesis.

This strategy has proven to be especially useful for the synthesis of trifluoromethyl substituted alkenes, being of special relevance since CF_3 containing compounds have found wide application in pharmaceuticals and agrochemicals.^[271] Nevertheless, only a limited number of methods for the synthesis of alkenyl- CF_3 bonds are known in the literature (Scheme 75). Among them, a Pd(dba)₂ (6 mol%) in combination with monodentate biaryl phosphine ligand *t*-BuXPhos (12 mol%) provides a series of trifluoromethylated compounds **272** from cyclohexenyl triflates and nonaflates **267** under mild reaction conditions with TMS CF_3 as a CF_3 source (Scheme 75a, left top).^[272] Similarly, other Cu-catalyzed methods are also known to construct desired Csp^2 - CF_3 bonds starting from alkenyl boronic acids **268** and Togni's reagent **271**, which was developed by Shen and coworkers (Scheme 75b, left middle).^[273] Furthermore, Hu and coworkers introduced a Lewis acid catalyzed ($CuF_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) strategy for the Csp^2 - CF_3 bond formations, using α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids **269** and **271** through decarboxylative fluoro-alkylation in good yields and *E/Z*-ratio (Scheme 75c, left middle).^[274] Similarly, Buchwald and co-workers disclosed a promising protocol for trifluoromethylation of potassium vinyl-trifluoroborate **270** in good yields and excellent *E/Z*-selectivities using iron(II)-catalyst and **271** as a CF_3 -source (Scheme 75d, left bottom).^[275]

Scheme 75. Selected examples of alkenyl trifluoromethylation.

In a visible light photoredox catalyzed variant developed by Cho and coworkers, the ATRA process and subsequent dehydrohalogenation were successfully combined using CF_3I and DBU (Scheme 75, right).^[270] This way, the trifluoromethylation of various alkenes became possible, and especially, terminal alkenes give rise exclusively to alkenyl- CF_3 products with *E*-configuration. It is particularly noteworthy that the reactions proceed efficiently in the presence of only 0.1 mol% $[Ru(phen)_3Cl_2]$ **206** photocatalyst, comparing favorably with classical transition metal cross coupling strategies.

7.3 ATRA-like (Radical/cationic pathway):

If the photoredox catalytic cycle is relevant in ATRA reactions, it should be possible to trap carbocations **255** (Scheme 69) generated this way by external nucleophiles, which opens the door to a wide range of vicinal difunctionalized compounds **274** (Scheme 76). Indeed, this strategy has been successfully developed for a considerable number of nucleophiles.^[276]

Scheme 76. ATRA-like (three-component) reaction.

7.3.1 Azidation of olefins (ATRA-like)

ATRA reactions can be terminated efficiently by azide, allowing a synthetically useful introduction nitrogen containing functional groups into alkenes. Masson and coworkers demonstrated a photochemical three-component (ATRA-like) azidotrifluoromethylation (Scheme 77, right),^[277] complementing thermal variants that achieve the coupling of α -iodoacetic acid ester with phenylsulfonyl azide (Scheme 77, left),^[278] which call for hexabutyliditin / (*t*BuON)₂ to sustain a radical chain reaction.^[279]

Scheme 77. Azidation of olefins.

This way, an efficient vicinal oxytrifluoromethylation of alkenes was also established by visible-light-driven organic photoredox catalysis.^[281] While the photochemical approach is attractive in avoiding organic tin reagents, the substrate scope demonstrated with respect to the alkylation agent R^1X **251** was limited to trifluoromethylation. Propagation of the reaction by a radical chain mechanism must be operating in the thermal variant (Path A or B), while in the photochemical process also a photocatalytic cycle is conceivable (Path C). A remarkable example (Scheme 78) how to efficiently utilize both, radical chain, as well as photoredox cycle, was demonstrated by Greaney and coworkers.^[280] They demonstrated the azidation of styrenes with the Zhdarkin reagent **276** catalyzed by $[Cu(dap)_2]Cl$. Under visible light irradiation, methoxy azides **277** are obtained, suggesting that a carbocation **280** is generated, which is trapped by methanol as an external nucleophile. However, if the reaction is carried out in the dark, exclusively diazidation to give rise to **278** is observed, being rationalized by radical **279**, which cannot be further oxidized under these reaction conditions but rather initiates a radical chain process with **276**.

Scheme 78. Azidation of olefins in dark and in presence of visible light irradiation.

7.3.2 Sulfonylation of olefins (ATRA-like)

β -Hydroxysulfones are proven scaffolds for pharmaceutically active candidates and useful building blocks for organic synthesis. In 2011, Taniguchi and coworkers showed a classical ATRA-like approach between sulfonylhydrazides **281** and alkenes **252** to give **285** utilizing catalytic amounts of $FeCl_3$ and oxygen (Scheme 79).^[282] The visible light mediated, iridium(III)-catalyzed addition of sulfonyl chlorides to alkenes in the presence of water provides an alternative to the targeted β -hydroxysulfones (Scheme 79).^[283] In both cases, the generation of sulfonyl radicals is proposed as key intermediates that undergo alkene addition. However, those are formed in the thermal variant by one-electron oxidation ($Fe(III) \rightarrow Fe(II)$) of sulfonyl hydrazides, while in the photochemical variant reduction of sulfonyl chlorides ($Ir^*(III) \rightarrow Ir(IV)$) takes place. Since sulfonyl chlorides can be synthesized by $Cu(dap)_2Cl$ catalyzed photochemical ATRA reaction between unactivated alkenes **284** and CF_3SO_2Cl ,^[265] a sequential process bringing together two alkenes via a sulfone group giving rise to trifluoromethylated β -hydroxysulfones **286** became possible.

Scheme 79. β -Hydroxysulfonylation of styrenes by classical and photocatalytic methods.

7.4 Anti-Markovnikov olefin hydrofunctionalization reactions (ATRA-like)

The net addition of $H-X$ (where $X = OR, O_2CR, NR_2$, halogen, etc) across olefins, either in Markovnikov or anti-Markovnikov regioselectivity is one of the standard transformations in organic synthesis.^[284] However, a general catalytic method for anti-Markovnikov hydrofunctionalization reactions of olefins was not available before 2012.^[285] Nicewicz and coworkers disclosed a photocatalytic anti-Markovnikov hydroetherification of alkenols employing Fukuzumi's photocatalyst **94** and a hydrogen atom donor.^[286] This reaction enables inter- or intramolecular anti-Markovnikov olefin hydroacetoxylation, hydro lactonization, hydroamination, and hydrotrifluoromethylations (Scheme 80).^[285,287] Furthermore, by employing this method, they were able to add mineral acids (e.g. HCl , HF , H_3PO_4 , and $MeSO_3H$) directly to the alkenes in anti-Markovnikov orientation (Scheme 80).^[288]

The authors^[285,289] proposed the oxidation of the olefin **287** by excited 94^* ($E_{ox} = +2.06$ V vs SCE) forming a radical cation followed by

REVIEW

nucleophilic addition of H-X **288** and subsequent hydrogen atom transfer affording the desired adduct **289**.

Scheme 80. Photocatalytic anti-Markovnikov addition of H-X to olefins.

8 Fluorination

8.1 Introduction of fluorine and fluorine-containing functional groups

Organofluorine compounds are prevalent in pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and organic materials.^[290] The introduction of fluorine groups into organic molecules drastically alters the electronic properties of compounds while keeping their steric demand similar to their hydrogen substituted analogs, which has especially beneficial effects on their metabolic stability by reducing their reactivity, e.g. towards oxidative degradation. Thus, developing methods that allow – ideally, at a late stage – the selective functionalization of complex molecules with fluorine and fluorine-containing functional groups is of great importance in organic synthesis.

A principle problem for such transformations is to find fluorine sources that have appropriate reactivity and selectivity. Fluoride containing reagents often do not show sufficient reactivity to be employed as nucleophiles or electrophiles or require special ligands for stabilization or activation that makes them not ideal from an atom economic point of view. The introduction of fluorinated substituents via radicals has developed as an important alternative due to their facile generation from

readily available precursors and their good selectivity and reactivity in the addition to sp^2 -hybridized carbon centers.

8.1.1 Trifluoromethylation of aromatic compounds (sp^2 - sp^3)

Methyl groups are ubiquitous in natural products and drugs, thus, their displacement by trifluoromethyl substituents often leads to analogs with improved biological activity as well as pharmacological properties. Especially, the introduction of CF_3 bonds into arenes and heteroarenes has been recognized as a powerful strategy for medicinal chemistry, and consequently, developing mild and versatile synthetic methods for trifluoromethylations has become an area of intense research efforts.^[291]

a) Direct trifluoromethylation of arenes via C-H activation

The direct trifluoromethylation of arenes via C-H activation can be achieved by employing a combination of $AgOTf/TMSCF_3$, generating $AgCF_3$ as the key intermediate.^[292] However, over stoichiometric amounts of $AgOTf$, as well as the formation of mixtures of regioisomers, limit the utility of this approach (Scheme 81, left).

Scheme 81. Silver mediated or photoredox catalyzed trifluoromethylation of arenes.

A photoredox catalyzed alternative for this transformation was reported by MacMillan and coworkers (Scheme 81, right),^[293] generating CF_3 -radicals from CF_3SO_2Cl via photoelectron transfer with concurrent extrusion of SO_2 and Cl^- . This methodology only requires low amounts of catalyst, moreover, improved regioselectivity for unsymmetrical substrates is observed compared to the approach discussed above. While CF_3SO_2Cl is commercially available at a reasonable cost, even more, attractive as a CF_3 source would be trifluoroacetic acid and readily available derivatives thereof. Stephenson and coworkers developed pyridine-*N*-oxide/trifluoroacetic anhydride highly efficient reagent, which allowed the trifluoromethylation of heteroarenes on kilogram scale in the presence of only 0.1 mol% $Ru(bpy)_3Cl_2$ **13** (Scheme 82).^[294]

Scheme 82. Large-scale, continuous-flow trifluoromethylation with trifluoroacetic anhydride.

b) Trifluoromethylation of aryl boronic acids

Aryl boronic acids **294** have become available in great variety due to their utility in palladium-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura coupling reactions. Thus, the discovery that the boron group can also be substituted by a trifluoromethyl group considerably broadens the scope for the synthesis of trifluoro methylated arenes and heteroarenes **291**.^[295] For example, in the presence of CuCl / TBHP the site-specific trifluoromethylation of aryl and heteroaryl boronic acids **294** with NaSO₂CF₃ has been reported by Sanford and coworkers to proceed in excellent yields (Scheme 83, left).^[296] Moving to a catalytic system, the combination of CuOAc/Ru(bpy)₃Cl₂ was effective for trifluoromethylation of boronic acids with trifluoromethyl iodide (Scheme 83, right).^[297] The mechanism of this reaction relies on the dual photo- and Cu-catalyzed cycles: As the key step is proposed the combination of a photoredox generated CF₃ radical with a Cu^{II} species to form a Cu^{III}(CF₃) intermediate. This crucial intermediate subsequently undergoes base-promoted transmetalation between Cu^{III} and the aryl boronic acid to form Cu^{III}(aryl)(CF₃). Finally, reductive elimination constructs the aryl-CF₃ bond with concurrent regeneration of the CuI catalyst.

Scheme 83. Cu/Ru-catalyzed trifluoromethylation of aryl boronic acids.

8.1.2 Trifluoromethylation of vinyl borates (sp²-sp³)

Along the lines discussed for aryl boronic acids, vinyl borates can also be trifluoromethylated by both non-photochemical and photochemical methods. In 2012, Buchwald and coworkers^[298] reported an iron(II)-catalyzed oxidative trifluoromethylation of potassium vinyl-

trifluoroborate **270** with Togni's reagent **271**, which provides rapid access to CF₃ substituted alkenes **295** in good yields and excellent *E/Z* ratios under mild conditions (Scheme 84, left). A photoredox catalyzed variant was published shortly after, substituting FeCl₂ by Ru(bpy)₃Cl₂/visible light irradiation (Scheme 84, right).^[299]

Scheme 84. Trifluoromethylation of potassium vinyl-trifluoroborate by the Fe^{II} and photoredox catalysis.

8.1.3 Hydro-trifluoromethylation of olefins (sp³-sp³)

In 1985, Yamamoto and coworkers reported the activation of CF₃I by trimethylaluminum^[300] for the synthesis of iodo-trifluorinated compounds **296** via an ATRA pathway with olefins **252**. Subsequent reduction of **296** by using a combination of *n*-Bu₃SnH and AIBN provided hydro-trifluorinated compound **297** (Scheme 85, left). The same sequence was reported by Dmowski and coworkers,^[301] achieving the initial ATRA with the combination of CF₃I/Na₂S₂O₄ followed by reduction by Zn/EtOH. A photocatalytic alternative was recently reported by Gouverneur and coworkers using Umemoto reagent **298**, which serves as a source for CF₃ radicals upon photoelectron transfer, while methanol serves as H-donor (Scheme 85, right).^[302]

Scheme 85. Hydrotrifluoromethylation of olefins by non-photocatalytic and photocatalytic methods.

8.1.4 Chlorotrifluoromethylation of olefins (sp³-sp³)

REVIEW

Recently, it was also shown that Cu^{II} catalyzed intermolecular chloro-trifluoromethylation of alkenes can be achieved by using simple CuBr₂ with Togni's reagent **271** as the CF₃ and thionyl chloride as the chloride source (Scheme 86, left).^[303] Initially, CF₃ radical formation is proposed to take place from **271** with the assistance of Cu^{II} by a single-electron-transfer (SET) process with the release of a Cu^{III} species. The CF₃ radical then adds to the alkene, and the resulting radical intermediate is oxidized to a carbocation with concurrent regeneration of the active Cu^{II} catalyst. Utilizing trifluoromethylsulfonyl chloride, the chloro-trifluoromethylation of alkenes can also be achieved under visible light photocatalysis both with ruthenium(II), as well as copper(I) based photocatalysts,^[50,81] being again initiated by electron transfer to CF₃SO₂Cl upon which CF₃ radicals are generated. Notably, Dolbier and coworkers demonstrated that difluoromethylsulfonyl chloride is also a suitable reagent for this process, delivering a CF₂H group to the alkene.^[304] It was also found that the electronic nature of the alkene is an important factor in the Cu(dap)₂Cl-catalyzed ATRA reaction. While Ru(bpy)₃Cl gives exclusively rise to trifluoromethylchlorination irrespective of the alkenes used (**300a**, X = Cl), trifluoromethylsulfonylation (**300b**, X=SO₂Cl) is observed when the ATRA reaction is carried out between CF₃SO₂Cl and unactivated alkenes (Scheme 86, right).^[265,266]

Scheme 86. Chlorotrifluoromethylation of olefins by non-photochemical and by photochemical method

8.1.5 α -Tri(per)fluoroalkylation of carbonyl compounds (sp³-sp³)

α -Trifluoroalkylations of carbonyl compounds cannot easily be achieved analogous to alkylations of enolates due to the low reactivity of perfluorinated alkyl halides towards nucleophiles. In contrast, perfluoroalkyl radicals show good reactivity with nucleophiles or in couplings with nucleophilic radicals. Based on these considerations, a successful strategy to achieve the trifluoromethylation of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds **301** was developed (Scheme 87a, top).^[305]

Scheme 87. Trifluoromethylation and perfluoroalkylation of carbonyl compounds

The key idea is that the sulfenic radical anion ($\bullet\text{SO}_2^-$) existing in equilibrium with the dithionite anion S₂O₄²⁻, can generate a CF₃ radical from CF₃I by a SET process, which in turn adds to the enolate of the 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds. Moving to a photoredox catalyzed and at the same time reporting an unprecedented enantioselective variant, MacMillan and coworkers^[10] elegantly accomplished the synthesis of α -trifluoromethylated or α -perfluoroalkylated aldehydes in high yields and excellent enantioselectivities (up to 99% yields and ee) (Scheme 87b, bottom). The key step is the addition of photochemically generated perfluoroalkyl radicals to the electron-rich alkene, in this case, a chiral modified enamine **305**.

8.1.6 Trifluoromethylthiolation (sp³-sp³ and sp²-sp³)

The trifluoromethylthio group (CF₃S) is also a prominent functionality, as it plays a vital role in drug chemistry due to its strong electron-withdrawing nature and high lipophilicity.^[306] There are several methods established for the introduction of a CF₃S group into organic compounds.^[307] In 2014, Rueping and co-workers disclosed the Cu(I) catalyzed trifluoromethylthiolation of boronic acids **308** utilizing the *N*-phthalimide derivative **307** as the CF₃S source (Scheme 88a, top).^[308] Very good substrate scope was demonstrated, making this methodology amenable not only for aryl boronic acids but also vinyl and alkynyl boronic acids. A photoredox catalyzed approach to the target compounds was reported by Noel and coworkers in the same year (Scheme 88b, bottom).^[309] Again, taking advantage of the high reactivity of nucleophiles towards trifluorothiomethyl radicals, aryl thiols **310** proved to be excellent coupling partners with the latter. The method was successfully transferred from batch to continuous micro(flow)reactors, thus dramatically shortening the reaction time from 5h to 1 min with an overall increase in yields due to better gas-liquid mass transfer and exposure of reaction mixture to visible light at room temperature (Scheme 88b, bottom).

Scheme 88. Trifluoromethylthiolation by non-photochemical and photochemical method.

8.2 Introduction of Fluorine atoms:

8.2.1 Aliphatic fluorination (sp^3-sp^3)

The selective incorporation of fluorine atoms into unactivated aliphatic compounds has a long standing history to be challenging.^[310] Designing SN-reactions utilizing fluoride – arguably the least expensive fluorine source - as nucleophile was hampered by the difficulties to strip it from its hydration shell, thus making it quite unreactive. Only recently, a number of breakthroughs were made by Sanford and coworkers to develop practical protocols that achieve the generation of fluoride nucleophiles water free, which then indeed prove to have excellent reactivity with aromatic as well as aliphatic compounds.^[311] In turn, electrophilic fluoride sources like commercially available Selectfluor allow the direct fluorination of C, H-bonds. In 2012, the group of Lectka^[312] demonstrated that copper(I) bisimine complex **312** catalyzes the fluorination of a broad variety of unactivated alkanes in presence of an anionic phase-transfer catalyst ($KB(C_6F_5)_4$) to obtain desired fluorine-functionalized products **314** in good to excellent yields (Scheme 89, left). Alternatively, alkane fluorination utilizing ultraviolet light (302 nm) and a photosensitizer, 1,2,4,5-tetracyanobenzene (TCB) **315**, also proceeds efficiently (Scheme 89, right).^[313] Chemoselectivity typical for a radical process, i.e. allylic, benzylic > tertiary > secondary, is observed, while primary aliphatic C, H-bonds could not be fluorinated.

Scheme 89. Aliphatic fluorination by non-photochemical and by photochemical methods

8.2.2 Benzylic fluorination (SP^3-SP^3)

The group of Lectka continued to expand the fluorination methodology described above. For the synthesis of mono-fluorinated products **317** from corresponding benzyl derivatives **316** with Selectfluor reagents **313a**, $Fe(acac)_2$ was found to be an efficient catalyst (Scheme 90).^[314] Chen and coworkers provided an operationally straightforward synthetic equivalent to the aforementioned method utilizing visible light photocatalysis.^[315] By this method, the selective formation of monofluorinated products **317** became possible using 9-fluorenone **319** as a photocatalyst (Scheme 90).

Scheme 90. Fe^{II} and (photo)catalyzed benzylic fluorination and difluorination

Furthermore, relatively challenging benzylic C–H difluorination was also possible with xanthone **320**. The excited photocatalyst generates a carbon-centered radical upon SET process via C–H activation; the resulting benzylic radical is quite persistent, which ultimately attacks the electrophilic fluorine atom of the selectfluor, generating a radical cation of the amine from selectfluor. The subsequent SET process occurs to form a quaternary ammonium ion with concurrent regeneration of the photocatalyst.

9. Conclusions

As obvious from our survey, the impact using visible light induced energy- or electron transfer on organic reactions varies significantly with the type of reaction. While in some cases the reaction conditions improve and become milder due to lower reaction temperatures compared to established methods, in others the advantage can be found in replacing toxic or expensive reagents. A smaller number of visible light photocatalytic reactions enable transformations, which were hitherto unknown or not practical to achieve.

Visible light photocatalysis has greatly expanded the possibilities for sp³-sp³ C–C bond forming reactions, being arguably the most challenging cross coupling reactions to achieve. The ultimate goal to carry out such transformations in an enantioselective fashion is also on the horizon given recent developments, which in some cases proceed even without the addition of photocatalysts or sensitizers via EDA complexes. In sp³-sp² cross coupling, the photoinduced electron transfer provides a facile alternative to classic transmetalation steps, which enables the reaction of substrates that were challenging so far. Photocatalytic protocols using silicates as coupling reagents and many dual catalytic arylations have been established. Widely used sp²-sp² cross coupling protocols benefit from alternative photocatalytic conditions at lower temperatures or without transition metal catalysts. The classic Meerwein arylation becomes more practical with higher product yields if done photocatalytic and even the challenging cross-coupling of chloro-arenes with arenes and heteroarenes can be mediated by conPET visible light photocatalysis at room temperature. Carbon-heteroatom bond formations benefit likewise from photocatalytic or dual catalytic protocols and proceed in many cases at milder reaction conditions. In particular, C–H aminations or amidations on arenes or in the α -position to carbonyl groups require complex reagents or directing groups under classic conditions. Photocatalytic protocols enable late stage C–H aminations or amidations on complex substrates and allow for a direct enantioselective C–H amination of carbonyls. For the introduction of carbon – sulfur bonds photocatalytic protocols help to avoid explosive intermediates or peroxides as stoichiometric oxidation reagents. Vinyl sulfones are accessible from sulfinates and alkenes without the use of transition metals.

A recent key impact of visible light protocols was reported for catalytic C–O bond formations. Here the sensitized energy transfer to a catalytically active nickel complex enabled endothermic reaction steps that were previously impossible. Another transformation that improved significantly by photocatalytic protocols is the α -functionalization to amines. Either via iminium intermediates or via radicals α to the amino group many selective transformations have been realized in a very practical way compared to previous thermal protocols. Decarboxylative cross-couplings were already well established using transition metal catalysis. Photocatalysis, in particular as a dual catalysis with nickel complexes, expanded the range of transformations and suitable substrates significantly.

In cycloadditions, visible light photoinduced electron transfer enables [4+2] reactions of electron rich dienes and alkenes. [2+2]

cycloadditions, classic UV photochemical reactions, proceed with visible light using suitable photocatalysts for energy- or electron transfer, and several [2+3] cycloadditions can be done at mild conditions. ATRA reactions typically require radical initiators and visible light photocatalysis can provide in many cases an alternative smart initiation of the chain reaction. Additionally, the photocatalysts can affect the course of the reaction, especially by using copper based complexes that can interact with radical intermediates by ligand transfer or by a rebound mechanism. Last, but not least, fluorination reactions of various kinds benefit from photocatalytic conditions as they proceed at milder reaction conditions, e.g. allowing the late stage functionalization of complex molecules with excellent functional group tolerance.

Overall, does visible light photocatalysis make a difference for organic synthesis? It certainly has considerably expanded the toolbox available for organic synthesis, but the difference or impact on improving or enabling a reaction cannot be judged in general and varies from marginal to transformative depending on the application.

A general advantage of photocatalytic methods compared to thermal chemistry is the possibility to perform most reactions at or below room temperature. Visible light can be selectively delivered to the photocatalyst as reaction energy source. Disadvantages of photocatalysis are the need for light sources and reaction vessels that allow irradiation. Many reactions in photocatalysis are radical processes and share therefore the benefits and limitations in functional group tolerance with classic radical chemistry.

Visible light photocatalysis has been already applied to most organic reaction classes with synergistic processes being particular beneficial. However, the selective energy input by photocatalysis into complex reaction systems holds promise for future work. Kinetically hindered or endothermic reactions may be enabled by the energy of light, which may open new reaction pathways in synthesis that are currently blocked by high energy barriers.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (GRK 1626, Chemical Photocatalysis) for financial support of their research. L.M. thanks the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation for a postdoctoral fellowship. S.K.P. thanks to DAAD for the Ph.D. fellowship.

Keywords: photocatalysis • thermal reactions • radical reactions • visible light • cross-coupling • cycloadditions

References

- [1] a) F. Teplý, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.* **2011**, *76*, 859; b) C. K. Prier, D. A. Rankic, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Chem. Rev.* **2013**, *113*, 5322; c) J. M. R. Narayanam, C. R. J. Stephenson, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, *40*, 102; d) D. Ravelli, S. Protti, M. Fagnoni, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 9850; e) K. L. Skubi, T. R. Blum, T. P. Yoon, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 10035; f) I. Ghosh, L. Marzo, A. Das, R. Shaikh, B. König, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1566; g) J. I. Day, K. Teegardin, J. Weaver, J. Chan, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2016**, *20*, 1156; h) J.-P. Goddard, C. Ollivier, L. Fensterbank, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1924; i) A. C. Hernandez-Perez, S. K. Collins, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1557; j) M. Majek, A. Jacobi von Wangelin, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 2316; k) D. C. Fabry, M. Rueping, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1969; l) J. C. Tellis, C. B. Kelly, D. N. Primer, M. Jouffroy, N. R. Patel, G. A. Molander, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1429; m) E. C. Gentry, R. R. Knowles, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1546; n) S. A. Morris, J. Wang, N. Zheng, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1957; o) S. P. Pitre, C. D. McTiernan, J. C. Scaiano,

- Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1320; p) M. H. Shaw, J. Twilton, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Org. Chem.* **2016**, *81*, 6898.
- [2] J. L. Namy, P. Girard, H. B. Kagan, *Nouv. J. Chim.* **1977**, *1*, 5.
- [3] M. Szostak, N. J. Fazakerley, D. Parmar, D. J. Procter, *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114*, 5959.
- [4] E. C. Gentry, R. R. Knowles, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1546.
- [5] K. T. Tarantino, P. Liu, R. R. Knowles, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 10022.
- [6] L. J. Rono, H. G. Yayla, D. Y. Wang, M. F. Armstrong, R. R. Knowles, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 17735.
- [7] A. G. Capacci, J. T. Malinowski, N. J. McAlpine, J. Kuhne, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Nat. Chem.* **2017**, *9*, 1073.
- [8] T. D. Beeson, A. Mastracchio, J.-B. Hong, K. Ashton, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2007**, *316*, 582.
- [9] D. A. Nicewicz, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2008**, *322*, 77.
- [10] D. A. Nagib, M. E. Scott, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 10875.
- [11] E. R. Welin, A. A. Warkentin, J. C. Conrad, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 9668.
- [12] H.-W. Shih, M. N. Vander Wal, R. L. Grange, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 13600.
- [13] B.-C. Hong, C.-W. Lin, W.-K. Liao, G.-H. Lee, *Org. Lett.* **2013**, *15*, 6258.
- [14] G. Cecere, C. M. König, J. L. Alleva, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 11521.
- [15] a) M. Cherevatskaya, M. Neumann, S. Fuldner, C. Harlander, S. Kummel, S. Dankesreiter, A. Pflitzner, K. Zeitler, B. König, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 4062; b) M. Neumann, S. Fuldner, B. König, K. Zeitler, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50*, 951; c) K. Fidaly, C. Ceballos, A. Falguières, M. S.-I. Veitia, A. Guy, C. Ferroud, *Green Chem.* **2012**, *14*, 1293; d) P. Wu, C. He, J. Wang, X. Peng, X. Li, Y. An, C. Duan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 14991; e) A. Gualandi, M. Marchini, L. Mengozzi, M. Natali, M. Lucarini, P. Ceroni, P. G. Cozzi, *ACS Catal.* **2015**, *5*, 5927.
- [16] E. Arceo, I. D. Jurberg, A. Alvarez-Fernandez, P. Melchiorre, *Nat. Chem.* **2013**, *5*, 750.
- [17] A. Bahamonde, P. Melchiorre, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 8019.
- [18] M. Silvi, E. Arceo, I. D. Jurberg, C. Cassani, P. Melchiorre, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 6120.
- [19] M. Silvi, C. Verrier, Y. P. Rey, L. Buzzetti, P. Melchiorre, *Nat. Chem.* **2017**, DOI:10.1038/nchem.2748.
- [20] H. Huo, X. Shen, C. Wang, L. Zhang, P. Rose, L.-A. Chen, K. Harms, M. Marsch, G. Hilt, E. Meggers, *Nature* **2014**, *515*, 100.
- [21] H. Huo, K. Harms, E. Meggers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 6936.
- [22] L. Li, C. Wang, R. Huang, M. R. Biscoe, *Nat. Chem.* **2013**, *5*, 607.
- [23] K. Tamao, K. Sumitani, Y. Kiso, M. Zembayashi, A. Fujioka, S. Kodama, I. Nakajima, A. Minato, M. Kumada, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* **1976**, *49*, 1958.
- [24] a) A. Rudolph, M. Lautens, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 2656; b) N. Miyaura, A. Suzuki, *Chem. Rev.* **1995**, *95*, 2457; c) O. N. I. Maluenda, *Molecules* **2015**, *20*, 7528.
- [25] C. Han, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 7532.
- [26] C. Vila, M. Giannerini, V. Hornillos, M. Fañanás-Mastral, B. L. Feringa, *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, *5*, 1361.
- [27] Y. Yasu, T. Koike, M. Akita, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2012**, *354*, 3414.
- [28] J. C. Tellis, D. N. Primer, G. A. Molander, *Science* **2014**, *345*, 433.
- [29] K. Tamao, Y. Kiso, K. Sumitani, M. Kumada, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1972**, *94*, 9268.
- [30] D. N. Primer, I. Karakaya, J. C. Tellis, G. A. Molander, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 2195.
- [31] V. Corce, L.-M. Chamoreau, E. Derat, J.-P. Goddard, C. Ollivier, L. Fensterbank, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 11414.
- [32] Y. Li, K. Miyazawa, T. Koike, M. Akita, *Org. Chem. Front.* **2015**, *2*, 319.
- [33] C. Lévêque, L. Chenneberg, V. Corcé, J.-P. Goddard, C. Ollivier, L. Fensterbank, *Org. Chem. Front.* **2016**, *3*, 462.
- [34] M. Jouffroy, D. N. Primer, G. A. Molander, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 475.
- [35] N. R. Patel, C. B. Kelly, M. Jouffroy, G. A. Molander, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, *18*, 764.
- [36] P. Zhang, C. C. Le, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 8084.
- [37] a) M. Ballestri, C. Chatgililoglu, K. B. Clark, D. Griller, B. Giese, B. Kopping, *J. Org. Chem.* **1991**, *56*, 678; b) C. Chatgililoglu, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **1992**, *25*, 188; c) J. L. C. Chatgililoglu, *Molecules* **2012**, *17*, 527.
- [38] D. R. Heitz, J. C. Tellis, G. A. Molander, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 12715.
- [39] a) C. Walling, M. J. Gibian, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1965**, *87*, 3361; b) W. J. Leigh, E. C. Lathioor, M. J. St. Pierre, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1996**, *118*, 12339; c) S. Kamijo, T. Hoshikawa, M. Inoue, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 5928; d) Y. Zhang, K. B. Teuscher, H. Ji, *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 2111.
- [40] D. Liu, C. Liu, H. Li, A. Lei, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 4453.
- [41] B. J. Shields, A. G. Doyle, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 12719.
- [42] M. H. Shaw, V. W. Shurtleff, J. A. Terrett, J. D. Cuthbertson, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2016**, *352*, 1304.
- [43] M. R. Heinrich, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2009**, *15*, 820.
- [44] T. Hering, D. P. Hari, B. König, *J. Org. Chem.* **2012**, *77*, 10347.
- [45] D. P. Hari, T. Hering, B. König, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 725.
- [46] C.-J. Yao, Q. Sun, N. Rastogi, B. König, *ACS Catal.* **2015**, *5*, 2935.
- [47] a) W. Guo, H.-G. Cheng, L.-Y. Chen, J. Xuan, Z.-J. Feng, J.-R. Chen, L.-Q. Lu, W.-J. Xiao, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2014**, *356*, 2787; b) W. Fu, F. Xu, Y. Fu, M. Zhu, J. Yu, C. Xu, D. Zou, *J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *78*, 12202; c) M. Bu, T. F. Niu, C. Cai, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *5*, 830.
- [48] B. Sahoo, M. N. Hopkinson, F. Glorius, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 5505.
- [49] X.-z. Shu, M. Zhang, Y. He, H. Frei, F. D. Toste, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 5844.
- [50] a) S. R. Neufeldt, M. S. Sanford, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2012**, *354*, 3517; b) Y.-X. Liu, D. Xue, J.-D. Wang, C.-J. Zhao, Q.-Z. Zou, C. Wang, J. Xiao, *Synlett* **2013**, *24*, 507; c) M. Tobisu, T. Furukawa, N. Chatani, *Chem. Lett.* **2013**, *42*, 1203.
- [51] A. Baralle, L. Fensterbank, J.-P. Goddard, C. Ollivier, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2013**, *19*, 10809.
- [52] G. Fumagalli, S. Boyd, M. F. Greaney, *Org. Lett.* **2013**, *15*, 4398.
- [53] M. N. Hopkinson, B. Sahoo, F. Glorius, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2014**, *356*, 2794.
- [54] Y. Yang, J. Lan, J. You, *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117*, 8787.
- [55] D. P. Hari, B. König, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 4734.
- [56] a) A. D. H. Cano-Yelo, *J. Photochem.* **1987**, *37*, 315; b) A. D. H. Cano-Yelo, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2* **1984**, 1093.
- [57] D. Kalyani, K. B. McMurtrey, S. R. Neufeldt, M. S. Sanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 18566.
- [58] D. P. Hari, P. Schroll, B. König, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 2958.
- [59] D. P. Hari, T. Hering, B. König, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, *14*, 5334.
- [60] Z. Wang, *John Wiley & Sons* **2010**, *419*, 1866.

- [61] P. Mastrorilli, C. F. Nobile, N. Taccardi, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2006**, 47, 4759.
- [62] P. Schroll, D. P. Hari, B. König, *ChemistryOpen* **2012**, 1, 130.
- [63] H. Jiang, C. Huang, J. Guo, C. Zeng, Y. Zhang, S. Yu, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2012**, 18, 15158.
- [64] I. Ghosh, T. Ghosh, J. I. Bardagi, B. König, *Science* **2014**, 346, 725.
- [65] Le Zeng, T. Liu, C. He, D. Shi, F. Zhang, C. Duan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, 138, 3958.
- [66] M. Majek, U. Faltermeier, B. Dick, R. Perez-Ruiz, A. Jacobi von Wangelin, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2015**, 21, 15496.
- [67] a) I. Ghosh, B. König, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, 55, 7676; *For a particular example of a classical method to form Csp²-Csp² bonds see:* b) Y. Haketa, Y. Tamura, N. Yasuda, H. Maeda, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, **2016**, 14, 8035.
- [68] a) S. van de Linde, I. Krstic, T. Prisner, S. Doose, M. Heilemann, M. Sauer, *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.* **2011**, 10, 499; b) S. van de Linde, A. Loschberger, T. Klein, M. Heidbreder, S. Wolter, M. Heilemann, M. Sauer, *Nat. Protoc.* **2011**, 6, 991.
- [69] L. Marzo, I. Ghosh, F. Esteban, B. König, *ACS Catal.* **2016**, 6, 6780.
- [70] A. Das, I. Ghosh, B. König, *Chem. Comm.* **2016**, 52, 8695.
- [71] a) R. Hili, A. K. Yudin, *Nat. Chem. Biol.* **2006**, 2, 284; b) R. J. Sundberg, *Indoles* **1996**, Academic: New York; c) E. C. Taylor, R. A. Jones, *Pyrroles* **1990**, Wiley: New York; d) A. Ricci, *Amino Group Chemistry: From Synthesis to the Life Science* **2008**, Wiley-VCH: Weinheim.
- [72] M. B. Smith, J. March, *March's Advanced Organic Chemistry: Reactions, mechanisms, and structure* **2001**, 5th ed.; Wiley: New York, 1552.
- [73] C. B. Kremer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1939**, 61, 1321.
- [74] a) D. S. Surry, S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2008**, 47, 6338; b) J. P. Wolfe, S. Wagaw, J.-F. Marcoux, S. L. Buchwald, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **1998**, 31, 805; c) J. F. Hartwig, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2008**, 41, 1534.
- [75] a) D. S. Surry, S. L. Buchwald, *Chem. Sci.* **2010**, 1, 13; b) F. Monnier, M. Taillefer, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, 48, 6954; c) D. Ma, Q. Cai, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2008**, 41, 1450; d) G. Evano, N. Blanchard, M. Toumi, *Chem. Rev.* **2008**, 108, 3054; e) S. V. Ley, A. W. Thomas, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2003**, 42, 5400.
- [76] a) J. Qiao, P. Lam, *Synthesis* **2011**, 2011, 829; b) K. Sanjeeva Rao, T.-S. Wu, *Tetrahedron* **2012**, 68, 7735.
- [77] a) S. H. Cho, J. Y. Kim, J. Kwak, S. Chang, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, 40, 5068; b) M.-L. Louillat, F. W. Patureau, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, 43, 901; c) J. L. Jeffrey, R. Sarpong, *Chem. Sci.* **2013**, 4, 4092.
- [78] a) J. C. Day, N. Govindaraj, D. S. McBain, P. S. Skell, J. M. Tanko, *J. Org. Chem.* **1986**, 51, 4959; b) U. Lüning, P. S. Skell, *Tetrahedron* **1985**, 41, 4289.
- [79] L. J. Allen, P. J. Cabrera, M. Lee, M. S. Sanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, 136, 5607.
- [80] K. Okada, K. Okamoto, N. Morita, K. Okubo, M. Oda, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1991**, 113, 9401.
- [81] K. Okada, K. Okubo, N. Morita, M. Oda, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1992**, 33, 7377.
- [82] Q. Qin, S. Yu, *Org. Lett.* **2014**, 16, 3504.
- [83] T. W. Greulich, C. G. Daniliuc, A. Studer, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, 17, 254.
- [84] E. Brachet, T. Ghosh, I. Ghosh, B. König, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, 6, 987.
- [85] A. U. Meyer, A. L. Berger, B. König, *Chem. Comm.* **2016**, 52, 10918.
- [86] a) K. Ohkubo, A. Fujimoto, S. Fukuzumi, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2013**, 117, 10719; b) K. Ohkubo, T. Kobayashi, S. Fukuzumi, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, 50, 8652.
- [87] N. A. Romero, K. A. Margrey, N. E. Tay, D. A. Nicewicz, *Science* **2015**, 349, 1326.
- [88] a) J. Hartwig, *Synlett* **1997**, 1997, 329; b) B. P. Fors, D. A. Watson, M. R. Biscoe, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, 130, 13552; c) A. T. Brusoe, J. F. Hartwig, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, 137, 8460.
- [89] E. B. Corcoran, M. T. Pirnot, S. Lin, S. D. Dreher, D. A. DiRocco, I. W. Davies, S. L. Buchwald, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2016**, 353, 279.
- [90] M. S. Oderinde, N. H. Jones, A. Juneau, M. Frenette, B. Aquila, S. Tentarelli, D. W. Robbins, J. W. Johannes, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, 55, 13219.
- [91] S. Z. Tasker, T. F. Jamison, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, 137, 9531.
- [92] a) R. S. NEALE, *Synthesis* **1971**, 1; b) M. Newcomb, T. M. Deeb, D. J. Marquardt, *Tetrahedron* **1990**, 46, 2317; c) J. H. Horner, F. N. Martinez, O. M. Musa, M. Newcomb, H. E. Shahin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1995**, 117, 11124; d) L. Stella, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **1983**, 22, 337; e) S. Z. Zard, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2008**, 37, 1603.
- [93] A. J. Musacchio, L. Q. Nguyen, G. H. Beard, R. R. Knowles, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, 136, 12217.
- [94] a) S. Y. Reece, D. G. Nocera, *Annu. Rev. Biochem.* **2009**, 78, 673; b) J. M. Mayer, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **2004**, 55, 363; c) S. Hammes-Schiffer, A. A. Stuchebrukhov, *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, 110, 6939.
- [95] a) C. R. Waidmann, A. J. M. Miller, C.-W. A. Ng, M. L. Scheuermann, T. R. Porter, T. A. Tronic, J. M. Mayer, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2012**, 5, 7771; b) J. J. Warren, T. A. Tronic, J. M. Mayer, *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, 110, 6961.
- [96] G. J. Choi, R. R. Knowles, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, 137, 9226.
- [97] A. J. Musacchio, B. C. Lainhart, X. Zhang, S. G. Naguib, T. C. Sherwood, R. R. Knowles, *Science* **2017**, 355, 727.
- [98] J. Davies, S. G. Booth, S. Essafi, R. A. W. Dryfe, D. Leonori, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, 54, 14017.
- [99] J. Davies, T. D. Svejstrup, D. Fernandez Reina, N. S. Sheikh, D. Leonori, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, 138, 8092.
- [100] a) P. C. Meltzer, D. Butler, J. R. Deschamps, B. K. Madras, *J. Med. Chem.* **2006**, 49, 1420; b) F. I. Carroll, B. E. Blough, P. Abraham, A. C. Mills, J. A. Holleman, S. A. Wolckenhauer, A. M. Decker, A. Landavazo, K. T. McElroy, H. A. Navarro et al., *J. Med. Chem.* **2009**, 52, 6768; c) M. C. Myers, J. Wang, J. A. Iera, J.-K. Bang, T. Hara, S. I. Saito, G. P. Zambetti, D. H. Appella, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, 127, 6152; d) R. Ando, T. Sakaki, Y. Morinaka, C. Takahashi, Y. Tamao **1994**, EP 603769 A1 19940629.
- [101] a) A. Ricci, *Group Chemistry: From Synthesis to the Life Sciences* **2008**, Ed.; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany; b) A. Ricci, *Modern Amination Methods* **2000**, Ed.; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany; c) R. M. Williams, *Synthesis of Optically Active α -Amino Acids* **1989**, Pergamon: Oxford, U.K.
- [102] a) J. M. Janey, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2005**, 44, 4292; b) T. Vilaivan, W. Bhanthumnavin, *Molecules* **2010**, 15, 917.
- [103] a) C. Bolm, A. Kasyan, K. Drauz, K. Günther, G. Raabe, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2000**, 39, 2288; b) M. E. Morilla, M. M. Díaz-Requejo, T. R. Belderrain, M. C. Nicasio, S. Trofimenko, P. J. Pérez, *Chem. Comm.* **2002**, 14, 2998; c) A. C. B. Burtoloso, C. R. D. Correia, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2004**, 45, 3355; d) J. R. Davies, P. D. Kane, C. J. Moody, *Tetrahedron* **2004**, 60, 3967; e) J. R. Davies, P. D. Kane, C. J. Moody, *J. Org. Chem.* **2005**, 70, 7305; f) H. Matsushita, S.-H. Lee, K. Yoshida, B. Clapham, G. Koch, J.

- Zimmermann, K. D. Janda, *Org. Lett.* **2004**, *6*, 4627; g) I. Aviv, Z. Gross, *Chem. Comm.* **2006**, 126, 4477.
- [104] X. Shen, K. Harms, M. Marsch, E. Meggers, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 9102.
- [105] S. E. Creutz, K. J. Lotito, G. C. Fu, J. C. Peters, *Science* **2012**, *338*, 647.
- [106] a) A. C. Bissember, R. J. Lundgren, S. E. Creutz, J. C. Peters, G. C. Fu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 5129; b) H.-Q. Do, S. Bachman, A. C. Bissember, J. C. Peters, G. C. Fu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 2162.
- [107] Q. M. Kainz, C. D. Matier, A. Bartoszewicz, S. L. Zultanski, J. C. Peters, G. C. Fu, *Science* **2016**, *351*, 681.
- [108] a) Y. Wang, S. Chackalamannil, Z. Hu, J.W. Clader, W. Greenlee, W. Billard, H. Binch, G. Crosby, V. Ruperto, R. A. Duffy, R. McQuade, J. E. Lachowicz, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* **2000**, *10*, 2247; b) B. Le Grand, C. Pignier, R. Letienne, F. Cuisiat, F. Rolland, A. Mas, B. Vacher, *J. Med. Chem.* **2008**, *51*, 3856; c) A. Gangjee, Y. Zeng, T. Talreja, J. J. McGuire, R. L. Kisliuk, S. F. Queener, *J. Med. Chem.* **2007**, *50*, 3046; d) L. Llauger, H. He, J. Kim, J. Aguirre, N. Rosen, U. Peters, P. Davies, G. Chiosis, *J. Med. Chem.* **2005**, *48*, 2892; e) Z.-Y. Sun, E. Botros, A.-D. Su, Y. Kim, E. Wang, N. Z. Baturay, C.-H. Kwon, *J. Med. Chem.* **2000**, *43*, 4160; f) G. Liu, J. T. Link, Z. Pei, E. B. Reilly, S. Leitza, B. Nguyen, K. C. Marsh, G. F. Okasinski, T. W. von Geldern, M. Ormes et al., *J. Med. Chem.* **2000**, *43*, 4025.
- [109] a) O. Stadler, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.* **1884**, *17*, 2075; b) J. H. Ziegler, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.* **1890**, *23*, 2469; c) G. E. Hilbert, T. B. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1929**, *51*, 1526.
- [110] a) T. Migita, T. Shimizu, Y. Asami, J.-i. Shiobara, Y. Kato, M. Kosugi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* **1980**, *53*, 1385; b) M. Murata, S. L. Buchwald, *Tetrahedron* **2004**, *60*, 7397; c) M. A. Fernandez-Rodriguez, Q. Shen, J. F. Hartwig, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2006**, *128*, 2180; d) G. Y. Li, G. Zheng, A. F. Noonan, *J. Org. Chem.* **2001**, *66*, 8677; e) P. Guan, C. Cao, Y. Liu, Y. Li, P. He, Q. Chen, G. Liu, Y. Shi, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2012**, *53*, 5987.
- [111] M. Majek, A. J. von Wangelin, *Chem. Comm.* **2013**, 49, 5507.
- [112] X. Wang, G. D. Cuny, T. Noel, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 7860.
- [113] M. S. Oderinde, M. Frenette, D. W. Robbins, B. Aquila, J. W. Johannes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 1760.
- [114] M. Jouffroy, C. B. Kelly, G. A. Molander, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, *18*, 876.
- [115] E. L. Tyson, M. S. Ament, T. P. Yoon, *J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *78*, 2046.
- [116] a) K. Oh, *Org. Lett.* **2007**, *9*, 2973; b) F. Hof, A. Schutz, C. Fah, S. Meyer, D. Bur, J. Liu, D. E. Goldberg, F. Diederich, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2006**, *45*, 2138; c) G. Pandey, K. N. Tiwari, V. G. Puranik, *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 3611; d) M. N. Noshi, A. El-awa, E. Torres, P. L. Fuchs, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, *129*, 11242; e) O. Arjona, R. Menchaca, J. Plumet, *Org. Lett.* **2001**, *3*, 107; f) D. J. Wardrop, J. Fritz, *Org. Lett.* **2006**, *8*, 3659; g) D. Enders, S. F. Müller, G. Raabe, J. Runsink, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2000**, 2000, 879; h) P. Mauleon, I. Alonso, M. R. Rivero, J. C. Carretero, *J. Org. Chem.* **2007**, *72*, 9924; i) S. Sulzer-Mosse, A. Alexakis, J. Mareda, G. Bollot, G. Bernardinelli, Y. Filinchuk, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2009**, *15*, 3204; j) H. Kumamoto, K. Deguchi, T. Wagata, Y. Furuya, Y. Odanaka, Y. Kitade, H. Tanaka, *Tetrahedron* **2009**, *65*, 8007; k) T. Nishimura, Y. Takiguchi, T. Hayashi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 9086; l) J.-N. Desrosiers, W. S. Bechara, A. B. Charette, *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 2315; m) J.-N. Desrosiers, A. B. Charette, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 5955; n) D. Ravelli, S. Montanaro, M. Zema, M. Fagnoni, A. Albini, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2011**, *353*, 3295.
- [117] a) R. Ettari, E. Nizi, M. E. Di Francesco, M.-A. Dude, G. Pradel, R. Vicik, T. Schirmeister, N. Micale, S. Grasso, M. Zappala, *J. Med. Chem.* **2008**, *51*, 988; b) J. J. Reddick, J. Cheng, W. R. Roush, *Org. Lett.* **2003**, *5*, 1967; c) J. T. Palmer, D. Rasnick, J. L. Klaus, D. Bromme, *J. Med. Chem.* **1995**, *38*, 3193.
- [118] B. A. Frankel, M. Bentley, R. G. Kruger, D. G. McCafferty, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 3404.
- [119] S. Liu, B. Zhou, H. Yang, Y. He, Z.-X. Jiang, S. Kumar, L. Wu, Z.-Y. Zhang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 8251.
- [120] a) S. Chodroff, W. F. Whitmore, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1950**, *72*, 1073; b) D. A. R. Happer, B. E. Steenson, *Synthesis* **1980**, 806.
- [121] I. C. Popoff, J. L. Dever, G. R. Leader, *J. Org. Chem.* **1969**, *34*, 1128.
- [122] a) N. Taniguchi, *Tetrahedron* **2014**, *70*, 1984; b) N. Taniguchi, *Synlett* **2011**, 1308.
- [123] W. Wei, J. Li, D. Yang, J. Wen, Y. Jiao, J. You, H. Wang, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2014**, *12*, 1861.
- [124] A. U. Meyer, S. Jäger, D. Prasad Hari, B. König, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2015**, *357*, 2050.
- [125] A. U. Meyer, K. Strakova, T. Slanina, B. König, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 8694.
- [126] W. Yang, S. Yang, P. Li, L. Wang, *Chem. Comm.* **2015**, 51, 7520.
- [127] a) K. Suwanborirux, K. Charupant, S. Amnuoyopol, S. Pummangura, A. Kubo, N. Saito, *J. Nat. Prod.* **2002**, *65*, 935; b) S. Kim, R. Kubec, R. A. Musah, *J. Ethnopharmacol.* **2006**, *104*, 188; c) I. Dini, G. C. Tenore, A. Dini, *J. Nat. Prod.* **2008**, *71*, 2036; d) M. El-Aasr, Y. Fujiwara, M. Takeya, T. Ikeda, S. Tsukamoto, M. Ono, D. Nakano, M. Okawa, J. Kinjo, H. Yoshimitsu et al., *J. Nat. Prod.* **2010**, *73*, 1306; e) T. P. Wyche, J. S. Piotrowski, Y. Hou, D. Braun, R. Deshpande, S. McIlwain, I. M. Ong, C. L. Myers, I. A. Guzei, W. M. Westler et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 11583.
- [128] T. Buronfosse, P. Moroni, E. Benoît, J. L. Rivière, *J. Biochem. Toxicol.* **1995**, *10*, 179.
- [129] a) J. Legros, J. R. Dehli, C. Bolm, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2005**, *347*, 19; b) R. Bentley, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2005**, *34*, 609.
- [130] a) T. Oyama, K. Naka, Y. Chujo, *Macromolecules* **1999**, *32*, 5240; b) M. Numata, Y. Aoyagi, Y. Tsuda, T. Yarita, A. Takatsu, *Anal. Chem.* **2007**, *79*, 9211.
- [131] a) C. Bolm, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2003**, *237*, 245; b) E. Wojaczynska, J. Wojaczynski, *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, *110*, 4303; c) P. K. Dorman, P. L. Leung, V. M. Dong, *Tetrahedron* **2011**, *67*, 4378; d) T. Neveselý, E. Svobodová, J. Chudoba, M. Sikorski, R. Cibulka, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2016**, *358*, 1654.
- [132] a) F. Xue, D. Wang, X. Li, B. Wan, *J. Org. Chem.* **2012**, *77*, 3071; b) Z. Han, D. Krishnamurthy, P. Grover, Q. K. Fang, X. Su, H. S. Wilkinson, Z.-H. Lu, D. Magiera, C. H. Senanayake, *Tetrahedron* **2005**, *61*, 6386; c) K. Hiroi, F. Kato, *Tetrahedron* **2001**, *57*, 1543.
- [133] G. A. Olah, J. Nishimura, *J. Org. Chem.* **1974**, *39*, 1203.
- [134] F. Yuste, A. H. Linares, V. M. Mastranzo, B. Ortiz, R. Sanchez-Obregon, A. Fraile, J. L. G. Ruano, *J. Org. Chem.* **2011**, *76*, 4635.
- [135] a) G. Maitro, S. Vogel, G. Prestat, D. Madec, G. Poli, *Org. Lett.* **2006**, *8*, 5951; b) G. Maitro, S. Vogel, M. Sadaoui, G. Prestat, D. Madec, G. Poli, *Org. Lett.* **2007**, *9*, 5493; c) E. Bernoud, G. Le Duc, X. Bantreil, G. Prestat, D. Madec, G. Poli, *Org. Lett.* **2010**, *12*, 320; d) T. Jia, A. Bellomo, K. E. L. Baina, S. D. Dreher, P. J. Walsh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 3740; e) T. Jia, A. Bellomo, S. Montel, M. Zhang, K. El Baina, B. Zheng, P. J. Walsh, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 260; f) T. Jia, M. Zhang, H. Jiang, C. Y.

- Wang, P. J. Walsh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 13887; g) T. Jia, M. Zhang, I. K. Sagamanova, C. Y. Wang, P. J. Walsh, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, *17*, 1168; h) H. Jiang, T. Jia, M. Zhang, P. J. Walsh, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, *18*, 972; i) F. Izquierdo, A. Chartoire, S. P. Nolan, *ACS Catal.* **2013**, *3*, 2190; j) F. Gelat, J.-F. Lohier, A.-C. Gaumont, S. Perrio, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2015**, *357*, 2011.
- [136] A. U. Meyer, A. Wimmer, B. König, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56*, 409.
- [137] J. Lindley, *Tetrahedron* **1984**, *40*, 1433.
- [138] a) M. Wolter, G. Nordmann, G. E. Job, S. L. Buchwald, *Org. Lett.* **2002**, *4*, 973; b) Y.-J. Chen, H.-H. Chen, *Org. Lett.* **2006**, *8*, 5609; c) R. A. Altman, A. Shafir, A. Choi, P. A. Lichtor, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Org. Chem.* **2008**, *73*, 284; d) J. Niu, H. Zhou, Z. Li, J. Xu, S. Hu, *J. Org. Chem.* **2008**, *73*, 7814.
- [139] a) A. Aranyos, D. W. Old, A. Kiyomori, J. P. Wolfe, J. P. Sadighi, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1999**, *121*, 4369; b) K. E. Torraca, X. Huang, C. A. Parrish, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 10770; c) N. Kataoka, Q. Shelby, J. P. Stambuli, J. F. Hartwig, *J. Org. Chem.* **2002**, *67*, 5553.
- [140] a) R. Han, G. L. Hillhouse, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1997**, *119*, 8135; b) P. T. Matsunaga, G. L. Hillhouse, A. L. Rheingold, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1993**, *115*, 2075; c) P. T. Matsunaga, J. C. Mavropoulos, G. L. Hillhouse, *Polyhedron* **1995**, *14*, 175.
- [141] J. A. Terrett, J. D. Cuthbertson, V. W. Shurtleff, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Nature* **2015**, *524*, 330.
- [142] E. R. Welin, C. Le, D. M. Arias-Rotondo, J. K. McCusker, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2017**, *355*, 380.
- [143] a) Y. H. Budnikova, O. G. Sinyashin, *Russ. Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *84*, 917; b) T. Chen, J.-S. Zhang, L.-B. Han, *Dalton Trans.* **2016**, *45*, 1843; c) A. L. Schwan, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2004**, *33*, 218; d) J.-L. Montchamp, Y. R. Dumond, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 510.
- [144] a) M. Kalek, M. Jezowska, J. Stawinski, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2009**, *351*, 3207; b) K. Xu, H. Hu, F. Yang, Y. Wu, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *2013*, 319; c) E. L. Deal, C. Petit, J.-L. Montchamp, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 3270; d) A. J. Bloomfield, S. B. Herzon, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, *14*, 4370.
- [145] a) T. Fu, H. Qiao, Z. Peng, G. Hu, X. Wu, Y. Gao, Y. Zhao, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2014**, *12*, 2895; b) M. Andaloussi, J. Lindh, J. Savmarker, P. J. R. Sjöberg, M. Larhed, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2009**, *15*, 13069.
- [146] M. Kalek, A. Ziadi, J. Stawinski, *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 4637.
- [147] W. C. Fu, C. M. So, F. Y. Kwong, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, *17*, 5906.
- [148] a) J. Ke, Y. Tang, H. Yi, Y. Li, Y. Cheng, C. Liu, A. Lei, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 6604; b) R. Zhuang, J. Xu, Z. Cai, G. Tang, M. Fang, Y. Zhao, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 2110; c) G. Hu, W. Chen, T. Fu, Z. Peng, H. Qiao, Y. Gao, Y. Zhao, *Org. Lett.* **2013**, *15*, 5362; d) J. Yang, T. Chen, L.-B. Han, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 1782; e) Y.-L. Zhao, G.-J. Wu, Y. Li, L.-X. Gao, F.-S. Han, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2012**, *18*, 9622; f) H. Zhang, X.-Y. Zhang, D.-Q. Dong, Z.-L. Wang, *RSC Adv.* **2015**, *5*, 52824; g) E. Jablonkai, G. Keglevich, *Curr. Org. Syn.* **2014**, *11*, 429; h) Y.-M. Li, S.-D. Yang, *Synlett* **2013**, *24*, 1739; i) C. Shen, G. Yang, W. Zhang, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2012**, *10*, 3500; j) Q. Yao, S. Levchik, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2006**, *47*, 277.
- [149] W.-J. Yoo, S. Kobayashi, *Green Chem.* **2013**, *15*, 1844.
- [150] J. Xuan, T.-T. Zeng, J.-R. Chen, L.-Q. Lu, W.-J. Xiao, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2015**, *21*, 4962.
- [151] Y. He, H. Wu, F. D. Toste, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 1194.
- [152] R. S. Shaikh, S. J. S. Düsel, B. König, *ACS Catal.* **2016**, *6*, 8410.
- [153] R. S. Shaikh, I. Ghosh, B. König, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2017**, *10.1002/chem.201701283*.
- [154] a) J. Fauvarque, *Pure Appl. Chem.* **1996**, *68*; b) A. F. Littke, G. C. Fu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2002**, *41*, 4176; c) G. W. Gribble, *J. Chem. Educ.* **2004**, *81*, 1441; d) H. Liu, X. Cao, Y. Wu, Q. Liao, A. J. Jimenez, F. Wurthner, H. Fu, *Chem. Comm.* **2014**, *50*, 4620.
- [155] a) M. J. Mintz, C. Walling, *Org. Synth.* **1973**, *5*, 184; b) W. D. Watson, *J. Org. Chem.* **1985**, *50*, 2145.
- [156] a) I. V. Koval', *Russ. J. Org. Chem.* **2002**, *38*, 301; b) F. Minisci, E. Vismara, F. Fontana, E. Platone, G. Faraci, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2* **1989**, 123; c) J. R. L. Smith, L. C. McKeer, J. M. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2* **1989**, 1537; d) S. M. Maddox, C. J. Nalbandian, D. E. Smith, J. L. Gustafson, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, *17*, 1042; e) Y. Zhang, K. Shibatomi, H. Yamamoto, *Synlett* **2005**, 2837; f) G. K. S. Prakash, T. Mathew, D. Hoole, P. M. Esteves, Q. Wang, G. Rasul, G. A. Olah, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 15770; g) D. Kalyani, A. R. Dick, W. Q. Anani, M. S. Sanford, *Org. Lett.* **2006**, *8*, 2523; h) K. Tanemura, T. Suzuki, Y. Nishida, K. Satsumabayashi, T. Horaguchi, *Chem. Lett.* **2003**, *32*, 932; i) Di Qiu, F. Mo, Z. Zheng, Y. Zhang, J. Wang, *Org. Lett.* **2010**, *12*, 5474.
- [157] T. Hering, B. Muhldorf, R. Wolf, B. König, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 5342.
- [158] F. H. Vaillancourt, E. Yeh, D. A. Vosburg, S. Garneau-Tsodikova, C. T. Walsh, *Chem. Rev.* **2006**, *106*, 3364.
- [159] K. Nakajima, Y. Miyake, Y. Nishibayashi, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1946.
- [160] C.-J. Li, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2009**, *42*, 335.
- [161] A. G. Condie, J. C. Gonzalez-Gomez, C. R. J. Stephenson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 1464.
- [162] D. P. Hari, B. König, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 3852.
- [163] M. Rueping, R. M. Koenigs, K. Poscharny, D. C. Fabry, D. Leonori, C. Vila, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2012**, *18*, 5170.
- [164] Z. Li, C.-J. Li, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 11810.
- [165] Z.-Q. Wang, M. Hu, X.-C. Huang, L.-B. Gong, Y.-X. Xie, J.-H. Li, *J. Org. Chem.* **2012**, *77*, 8705.
- [166] S. Zhu, M. Rueping, *Chem. Comm.* **2012**, *48*, 11960.
- [167] M. Rueping, C. Vila, R. M. Koenigs, K. Poscharny, D. C. Fabry, *Chem. Comm.* **2011**, *47*, 2360.
- [168] G. Bergonzini, C. S. Schindler, C.-J. Wallentin, E. N. Jacobsen, C. R. J. Stephenson, *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, *5*, 112.
- [169] D. A. DiRocco, T. Rovis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 8094.
- [170] a) K. R. Campos, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2007**, *36*, 1069; b) M. D. Curtis, P. Beak, *J. Org. Chem.* **1999**, *64*, 2996.
- [171] A. McNally, C. K. Prier, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2011**, *334*, 1114.
- [172] P. Kohls, D. Jadhav, G. Pandey, O. Reiser, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, *14*, 672.
- [173] L. Ruiz Espelt, E. M. Wiensch, T. P. Yoon, *J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *78*, 4107.
- [174] Y. Miyake, K. Nakajima, Y. Nishibayashi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 3338.
- [175] S. Zhu, A. Das, L. Bui, H. Zhou, D. P. Curran, M. Rueping, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 1823.
- [176] G. M. Allan, A. F. Parsons, J.-F. Pons, *Synlett* **2002**, 1431.
- [177] I. Prediger, T. Weiss, O. Reiser, *Synthesis* **2008**, 2191.
- [178] S. K. Pagire, O. Reiser, *Green Chem.* **2017**, *19*, 1721.
- [179] a) H. Hunsdiecker, C. Hunsdiecker, E. Vogt, US 2176181 **1939**; b) H. Hunsdiecker, C. Hunsdiecker, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges. B* **1942**, *75*, 291; c) R. G. Johnson, R. K. Ingham, *Chem. Rev.* **1956**, *56*, 219.
- [180] M. O. Konev, E. R. Jarvo, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 11340.

- [181] Y. Miyake, K. Nakajima, Y. Nishibayashi, *Chem. Comm.* **2013**, 49, 7854.
- [182] Z. Zuo, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 5257.
- [183] L. Chu, C. Ohta, Z. Zuo, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 10886.
- [184] A. Noble, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 11602.
- [185] Z. Zuo, D. T. Ahneman, L. Chu, J. A. Terrett, A. G. Doyle, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Science* **2014**, *345*, 437.
- [186] A. Noble, S. J. McCarver, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 624.
- [187] C. P. Johnston, R. T. Smith, S. Allmendinger, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Nature* **2016**, *536*, 322.
- [188] L. Fan, J. Jia, H. Hou, Q. Lefebvre, M. Rueping, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 16437.
- [189] S. B. Lang, K. M. O'Nele, J. A. Tunge, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 13606.
- [190] a) J. Zhang, C. Stanciu, B. Wang, M. M. Hussain, C.-S. Da, P. J. Carroll, S. D. Dreher, P. J. Walsh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 20552; b) B. M. Trost, D. A. Thaisrivongs, J. Hartwig, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 12439; c) B. M. Trost, D. A. Thaisrivongs, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 12056; d) S. R. Waetzig, J. A. Tunge, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, *129*, 14860.
- [191] a) G. L. Lackner, K. W. Quasdorf, L. E. Overman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 15342; b) G. L. Lackner, K. W. Quasdorf, G. Pratsch, L. E. Overman, *J. Org. Chem.* **2015**, *80*, 6012; c) G. Pratsch, G. L. Lackner, L. E. Overman, *J. Org. Chem.* **2015**, *80*, 6025; d) C. R. Jamison, L. E. Overman, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1578.
- [192] G. Kachkovskiy, C. Faderl, O. Reiser, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2013**, *355*, 2240.
- [193] J. Schwarz, B. König, *Green Chem.* **2016**, *18*, 4743.
- [194] L.-N. Guo, H. Wang, X.-H. Duan, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2016**, *14*, 7380.
- [195] J. Liu, Q. Liu, H. Yi, C. Qin, R. Bai, X. Qi, Y. Lan, A. Lei, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 502.
- [196] G.-Z. Wang, R. Shang, W.-M. Cheng, Y. Fu, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, *17*, 4830.
- [197] L. Chu, J. M. Lipshultz, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 7929.
- [198] C. C. Le, D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 11938.
- [199] C. L. Joe, A. G. Doyle, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 4040.
- [200] R. Remy, C. G. Bochet, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 9816.
- [201] a) W. C. Herndon, *Chem. Rev.* **1972**, *72*, 157; b) R. Huisgen, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **1968**, *7*, 321.
- [202] T. P. Yoon, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 2307.
- [203] S. Poplata, A. Troster, Y.-Q. Zou, T. Bach, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 9748.
- [204] K. L. Skubi, T. R. Blum, T. P. Yoon, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 10035.
- [205] F. Mayr, R. Brimiouille, T. Bach, *J. Org. Chem.* **2016**, *81*, 6965.
- [206] a) B. R. Bear, S. M. Sparks, K. J. Shea, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2001**, *40*, 820; b) K. C. Nicolaou, S. A. Snyder, T. Montagnon, G. Vassilikogiannakis, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2002**, *41*, 1668; c) E. M. Stocking, R. M. Williams, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2003**, *42*, 3078; d) K.-I. Takao, R. Munakata, K.-i. Tadano, *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, *105*, 4779.
- [207] D. W. Reynolds, N. L. Bauld, *Tetrahedron* **1986**, *42*, 6189.
- [208] a) S. M. Stevenson, M. P. Shores, E. M. Ferreira, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 6506; b) R. F. Higgins, S. M. Fatur, S. G. Shepard, S. M. Stevenson, D. J. Boston, E. M. Ferreira, N. H. Damrauer, A. K. Rappe, M. P. Shores, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 5451.
- [209] S. Lin, M. A. Ischay, C. G. Fry, T. P. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 19350.
- [210] G. Pandey, P. Banerjee, S. R. Gadre, *Chem. Rev.* **2006**, *106*, 4484.
- [211] A. G. Amador, E. M. Sherbrook, T. P. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 4722.
- [212] B. C. Boren, S. Narayan, L. K. Rasmussen, L. Zhang, H. Zhao, Z. Lin, G. Jia, V. V. Fokin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 8923.
- [213] a) T. Hashimoto, K. Maruoka, *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115*, 5366; b) A. Padwa, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **1976**, *15*, 123; c) J. Adrio, J. C. Carretero, *Chem. Comm.* **2014**, *50*, 12434; d) A. G. Meyer, J. H. Ryan, *Molecules* **2016**, *21*, 935.
- [214] a) D. Curran, J. Grimshaw, S. D. Perera, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **1991**, *20*, 391; b) S. J. Higgins, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **1997**, *26*, 247; c) B. A. Trofimov, L. N. Sobenina, A. P. Demenev, A. I. Mikhaleva, *Chem. Rev.* **2004**, *104*, 2481; d) H. Fan, J. Peng, M. T. Hamann, J.-F. Hu, *Chem. Rev.* **2008**, *108*, 264.
- [215] a) E. Baltazzi, L. I. Krimen, *Chem. Rev.* **1963**, *63*, 511; b) F. J. Leeper, J. M. Kelly, *Org. Prep. Proc. Int.* **2013**, *45*, 171; c) V. Estevez, M. Villacampa, J. C. Menendez, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2010**, *39*, 4402.
- [216] K.-I. Washizuka, S. Minakata, I. Ryu, M. Komatsu, *Tetrahedron* **1999**, *55*, 12969.
- [217] A. R. Katritzky, G. J. Hitchings, X. Zhao, *Synthesis* **1991**, 863.
- [218] a) J. Xuan, X.-D. Xia, T.-T. Zeng, Z.-J. Feng, J.-R. Chen, L.-Q. Lu, W.-J. Xiao, *Angew. Chem.* **2014**, *126*, 5759; b) J.-R. Chen, X.-Q. Hu, L.-Q. Lu, W.-J. Xiao, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1911.
- [219] a) C. Lamberth, *Heterocycles* **2007**, *71*, 1467; b) C. B. Vicentini, D. Mares, A. Tartari, M. Manfrini, G. Forlani, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2004**, *52*, 1898.
- [220] a) Z. Sui, J. Guan, M. P. Ferro, K. McCoy, M. P. Wachter, W. V. Murray, M. Singer, M. Steber, D. M. Ritchie, D. C. Argentieri, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* **2000**, *10*, 601; b) A. A. Bekhit, T. Abdel-Aziem, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2004**, *12*, 1935; c) C. Selvam, S. M. Jachak, R. Thilagavathi, A. K. Chakraborti, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* **2005**, *15*, 1793; d) R. Katoch-Rouse, O. A. Pavlova, T. Caulder, A. F. Hoffman, A. G. Mukhin, A. G. Horti, *J. Med. Chem.* **2003**, *46*, 642; e) S. R. Stauffer, C. J. Coletta, R. Tedesco, G. Nishiguchi, K. Carlson, J. Sun, B. S. Katzenellenbogen, J. A. Katzenellenbogen, *J. Med. Chem.* **2000**, *43*, 4934; f) S. R. Stauffer, Y. Huang, C. J. Coletta, R. Tedesco, J. A. Katzenellenbogen, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2001**, *9*, 141; g) A. Jamwal, A. Javed, V. Bhardwaj, *J. Pharm. BioSci.* **2013**, *3*, 114.
- [221] a) K. Makino, H. S. Kim, Y. Kurasawa, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.* **1999**, *36*, 321; b) S. Fustero, A. Simón-Fuentes, J. F. Sanz-Cervera, *Org. Prep. Proc. Int.* **2009**, *41*, 253.
- [222] C. Ma, Y. Li, P. Wen, R. Yan, Z. Ren, G. Huang, *Synlett* **2011**, 1321.
- [223] a) G. Brasche, S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2008**, *47*, 1932; b) S. Ueda, H. Nagasawa, *Angew. Chem.* **2008**, *120*, 6511.
- [224] Y. Ding, T. Zhang, Q.-Y. Chen, C. Zhu, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, *18*, 4206.
- [225] H. C. Kolb, M. G. Finn, K. B. Sharpless, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2001**, *40*, 2004.
- [226] G. C. Tron, T. Pirali, R. A. Billington, P. L. Canonico, G. Sorba, A. A. Genazzani, *Med. Res. Rev.* **2008**, *28*, 278.
- [227] C. W. Tornøe, C. Christensen, M. Meldal, *J. Org. Chem.* **2002**, *67*, 3057.
- [228] a) M. Liu, O. Reiser, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 1102; b) J. E. Moses, A. D. Moorhouse, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2007**, *36*, 1249; c) E. J. Yoo, M.

- Ahlquist, S. H. Kim, I. Bae, V. V. Fokin, K. B. Sharpless, S. Chang, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 1730.
- [229] a) V. V. Rostovtsev, L. G. Green, V. V. Fokin, K. B. Sharpless, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2002**, *41*, 2596; b) J. Kalisiak, K. B. Sharpless, V. V. Fokin, *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 3171.
- [230] S. C. Ritter, B. König, *Chem. Commun.* **2006**, 4694.
- [231] P. Kumar, C. Joshi, A. K. Srivastava, P. Gupta, R. Boukherroub, S. L. Jain, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2016**, *4*, 69.
- [232] M. W. Smith P. S. Baran, *Science* **2015**, *349*, 925.
- [233] a) B. B. Snider, R. A. H. F. Hui, Y. S. Kulkarni, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1985**, *107*, 2194; b) T. T. Tidwell, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2005**, *44*, 5778; c) T. T. Tidwell, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2006**, *2006*, 563; d) C. Rasik, M. Brown, *Synlett* **2014**, *25*, 760.
- [234] J. M. Hoyt, V. A. Schmidt, A. M. Tondreau, P. J. Chirik, *Science* **2015**, *349*, 960.
- [235] E. Kim, J. K. Kochi, M. Christl, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **1990**, *123*, 1209.
- [236] M. D'Auria, R. Racioppi, *Molecules* **2013**, *18*, 11384.
- [237] a) G. Pandey, S. Hajra, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **1994**, *33*, 1169; b) G. Pandey, M. K. Ghorai, S. Hajra, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1998**, *39*, 1831; c) G. Pandey, G. Kumaraswamy, U. T. Bhalerao, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1989**, *30*, 6059.
- [238] M. A. Ischay, Z. Lu, T. P. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 8572.
- [239] T. P. Yoon, M. A. Ischay, J. Du, *Nat. Chem.* **2010**, *2*, 527.
- [240] J. Du, K. L. Skubi, D. M. Schultz, T. P. Yoon, *Science* **2014**, *344*, 392.
- [241] V. Mojr, E. Svobodova, K. Strakova, T. Nevesely, J. Chudoba, H. Dvorakova, R. Cibulka, *Chem. Comm.* **2015**, *51*, 12036.
- [242] a) N. J. Turro, *J. Chem. Educ.* **1966**, *43*, 13; b) W. L. Dilling, *Chem. Rev.* **1969**, *69*, 845.
- [243] N. Gaß, H.-A. Wagenknecht, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2015**, *2015*, 6661.
- [244] a) R. R. Islagulov, F. N. Castellano, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2006**, *45*, 5957; b) H. Ikezawa, C. Kutal, K. Yasufuku, H. Yamazaki, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1986**, *108*, 1589.
- [245] Z. Lu, T. P. Yoon, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 10329.
- [246] S. K. Pagire, A. Hossain, L. Traub, S. Kerres, O. Reiser, *Chem. Commun.* **2017**, *53*, 12072.
- [247] T. Lei, C. Zhou, M.-Y. Huang, L.-M. Zhao, B. Yang, C. Ye, H. Xiao, Q.-Y. Meng, V. Ramamurthy, C.-H. Tung et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56*, 15407.
- [248] M. S. Kharasch, E. V. Jensen, W. H. Urry, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1945**, *67*, 1626.
- [249] M. S. Kharasch, E. V. Jensen, W. H. Urry, *Science* **1945**, *102*, 128.
- [250] a) S. Paria, O. Reiser, *ChemCatChem* **2014**, *6*, 2477; b) T. Courant, G. Masson, *J. Org. Chem.* **2016**, *81*, 6945; c) J. M. Muñoz-Molina, T. R. Belderrain, P. J. Pérez, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2011**, 3155.
- [251] O. Reiser, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1990.
- [252] M. N. C. Balili, T. Pintauer, *Dalton Trans.* **2011**, *40*, 3060.
- [253] a) D. P. Curran, E. Bosch, J. Kaplan, M. Newcomb, *J. Org. Chem.* **1989**, *54*, 1826; b) D. P. Curran, C. T. Chang, *J. Org. Chem.* **1989**, *54*, 3140; c) D. P. Curran, M. H. Chen, E. Spletzer, C. M. Seong, C. T. Chang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1989**, *111*, 8872; d) D. P. Curran, C. M. Seong, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1990**, *112*, 9401; e) D. P. Curran, J. Tamine, *J. Org. Chem.* **1991**, *56*, 2746.
- [254] a) H. Yorimitsu, T. Nakamura, H. Shinokubo, K. Oshima, *J. Org. Chem.* **1998**, *63*, 8604; b) H. Yorimitsu, T. Nakamura, H. Shinokubo, K. Oshima, K. Omoto, H. Fujimoto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2000**, *122*, 11041; c) H. Yorimitsu, H. Shinokubo, S. Matsubara, K. Oshima, K. Omoto, H. Fujimoto, *J. Org. Chem.* **2001**, *66*, 7776.
- [255] J. Baraut, A. Massard, F. Chotard, E. Bodio, M. Picquet, P. Richard, Y. Borguet, F. Nicks, A. Demonceau, P. Le Gendre, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2015**, 2671.
- [256] C.-J. Wallentin, J. D. Nguyen, P. Finkbeiner, C. R. J. Stephenson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 8875.
- [257] M. A. Cismesia, T. P. Yoon, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 5426.
- [258] J. M. Munoz-Molina, T. R. Belderrain, P. J. Perez, *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, *49*, 642.
- [259] a) M. Mitani, I. Kato, K. Koyama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1983**, *105*, 6719; b) M. Mitani, M. Nakayama, K. Koyama, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1980**, *21*, 4457.
- [260] M. Pirtsch, S. Paria, T. Matsuno, H. Isobe, O. Reiser, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2012**, *18*, 7336.
- [261] J. -M. Kern. J. -P. Sauvage, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Comm.* **1987**, 546.
- [262] M. Knorn, T. Rawner, R. Czerwieniec, O. Reiser, *ACS Catal.* **2015**, *5*, 5186.
- [263] S. Paria, M. Pirtsch, V. Kais, O. Reiser, *Synthesis* **2013**, *45*, 2689.
- [264] P. T. G. Rabet, G. Fumagalli, S. Boyd, M. F. Greaney, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, *18*, 1646.
- [265] D. B. Bagal, G. Kachkovskiy, M. Knorn, T. Rawner, B. M. Bhanage, O. Reiser, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 6999.
- [266] T. Rawner, M. Knorn, E. Lutsker, A. Hossain, O. Reiser, *J. Org. Chem.* **2016**, *81*, 7139.
- [267] C. C. C. Johansson Seechurn, M. O. Kitching, T. J. Colacot, V. Snieckus, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 5062.
- [268] P. A. Byrne, D. G. Gilheany, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 6670.
- [269] S. J. Connon, S. Blechert, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2003**, *42*, 1900.
- [270] N. Iqbal, S. Choi, E. Kim, E. J. Cho, *J. Org. Chem.* **2012**, *77*, 11383.
- [271] a) K. Muller, C. Faeh, F. Diederich, *Science* **2007**, *317*, 1881; b) D. O'Hagan, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2008**, *37*, 308; c) S. Purser, P. R. Moore, S. Swallow, V. Gouverneur, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2008**, *37*, 320.
- [272] E. J. Cho, S. L. Buchwald, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 6552.
- [273] T. Liu, Q. Shen, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 2342.
- [274] Z. He, T. Luo, M. Hu, Y. Cao, J. Hu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 3944.
- [275] A. T. Parsons, T. D. Senecal, S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 2947.
- [276] T. Koike, M. Akita, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 1937.
- [277] G. Dagousset, A. Carboni, E. Magnier, G. Masson, *Org. Lett.* **2014**, *16*, 4340.
- [278] a) D. H. R. Barton, J. C. Jaszberenyi, E. A. Theodorakis, J. H. Reibenspies, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1993**, *115*, 8050; b) C. Ollivier, P. Renaud, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 4717.
- [279] a) P. Renaud, C. Ollivier, P. Panchaud, *Angew. Chem.* **2002**, *114*, 3610; b) E. Godineau, Y. Landais, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2009**, *15*, 3044.
- [280] G. Fumagalli, P. T. G. Rabet, S. Boyd, M. F. Greaney, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 11481.
- [281] Y. Yasu, T. Koike, M. Akita, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 9567.
- [282] T. Taniguchi, A. Idota, H. Ishibashi, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2011**, *9*, 3151.
- [283] S. K. Pagire, S. Paria, O. Reiser, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, *18*, 2106.
- [284] a) R. W. Hoffmann, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2016**, *45*, 577; b) L.-B. Han, M. Tanaka, *Chem. Comm.* **1999**, 395; c) S. Zhu, N. Niljianskul, S. L. Buchwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 15746; d) R. P. Rucker, A. M. Whittaker, H. Dang, G. Lalic, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 6571; e) A. E. Strom, J. F. Hartwig, *J. Org. Chem.* **2013**, *78*, 8909; f) G. Dong, P. Teo, Z. K. Wickens, R. H. Grubbs,

- Science* **2011**, 333, 1609; g) M. Utsunomiya, J. F. Hartwig, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, 126, 2702; h) M. Beller, J. Seayad, A. Tillack, H. Jiao, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2004**, 43, 3368.
- [285] K. A. Margrey, D. A. Nicewicz, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, 49, 1997.
- [286] D. S. Hamilton, D. A. Nicewicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, 134, 18577.
- [287] a) D. J. Wilger, N. J. Gesmundo, D. A. Nicewicz, *Chem. Sci.* **2013**, 4, 3160; b) P. D. Morse, D. A. Nicewicz, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, 6, 270; c) T. M. Nguyen, D. A. Nicewicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, 135, 9588.
- [288] D. J. Wilger, J.-M. M. Grandjean, T. R. Lammert, D. A. Nicewicz, *Nat. Chem.* **2014**, 6, 720.
- [289] N. A. Romero, D. A. Nicewicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, 136, 17024.
- [290] a) M. Schlosser, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2006**, 45, 5432; b) K. Müller, C. Faeh, F. Diederich, *Science* **2007**, 317, 1881; c) S. Purser, P. R. Moore, S. Swallow, V. Gouverneur, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2008**, 37, 320; d) O. A. Tomashenko, V. V. Grushin, *Chem. Rev.* **2011**, 111, 4475.
- [291] a) V. V. Grushin, W. J. Marshall, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2006**, 128, 4632; b) E. J. Cho, T. D. Senecal, T. Kinzel, Y. Zhang, D. A. Watson, S. L. Buchwald, *Science* **2010**, 328, 1679; c) G. G. Dubinina, H. Furutachi, J. Vivic, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, 130, 8600; d) C. P. Zhang, Z. L. Wang, Q. Y. Chen, C. T. Zhang, Y. C. Gu, J. C. Xiao, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, 50, 1896; e) K. Miura, M. Taniguchi, K. Nozaki, K. Oshima, K. Utimoto, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1990**, 31, 6391; f) I. Kietlsch, P. Eisenberger, A. Togni, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2007**, 46, 754; g) T. S. Umemoto, S. Ishihara, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1993**, 115, 2156; h) K. M. Y. Itoh, *Org. Lett.* **2005**, 7, 4883.
- [292] Y. Ye, S. H. Lee, M. S. Sanford, *Org. Lett.* **2011**, 13, 5464.
- [293] D. A. Nagib, D. W. C. MacMillan, *Nature* **2011**, 480, 224.
- [294] a) J. W. Beatty, J. J. Douglas, R. Miller, R. C. McAtee, K. P. Cole, C. R. J. Stephenson, *Chem* **2016**, 1, 456; b) O. Reiser, *Chem* **2016**, 1, 344.
- [295] a) E. J. Cho, T. D. Senecal, T. Kinzel, Y. Zhang, *Science* **2010**, 328, 1679; b) G. G. Dubinina, J. Ogikubo, D. A. Vivic, *Organometallics* **2008**, 27, 6233.
- [296] Y. Y., Stefan, A. Kunzi, M. S. Sanford, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, 14, 4979.
- [297] Y. Ye, M. S. Sanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, 134, 9034.
- [298] A. T. Parsons, T. D. Senecal and S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, 51, 2947.
- [299] Y. Yasu, T. Koike, M. Akita, *Chem. Comm.* **2013**, 49, 2037.
- [300] K. Maruoka, H. Sano, Y. Fukutani, H. Yamamoto, *Chem. Lett.* **1985**, 1689.
- [301] W. D. J. Ignatowska, *J. Fluorine Chem.* **2007**, 128, 997.
- [302] S. Mizuta, S. Verhoog, K. M. Engle, T. Khotavivattana, M. O'Duill, K. Wheelhouse, G. Rassias, M. Medebielle, V. Gouverneur, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, 135, 2505.
- [303] M. Fu, L. Chen, Y. Jiang, Z.-X. Jiang, Z. Yang, *Org. Lett.* **2016**, 18, 348.
- [304] a) Z. Zhang, X. Tang, C. S. Thomason, W. R. Dolbier, JR, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, 17, 3528; b) X.-J. Tang, C. S. Thomason, W. R. Dolbier, JR, *Org. Lett.* **2014**, 16, 4594.
- [305] V. Petrik, D. Cahard, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2007**, 48, 3327.
- [306] a) C. Hansch, A. Leo, R. W. Taft, *Chem. Rev.* **1991**, 91, 165; b) L. M. Yagupol'skii, A. Y. Ilchenko, N. V. Kondratenko, *Russ. Chem. Rev.* **1974**, 43, 32; c) F. Leroux, P. Jeschke, M. Schlosser, *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, 105, 827.
- [307] a) V. N. Boiko, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.* **2010**, 6, 880; b) T. B. A. Tlili, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, 52, 6818.
- [308] R. Pluta, P. Nikolaienko, M. Rueping, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, 53, 1650.
- [309] N. J. W. Straathof, B. J. P. Tegelbeckers, V. Hessel, X. Wang, T. Noel, *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, 5, 4768.
- [310] a) H. M. Davies, A. R. Dick, *Top. Curr. Chem.* **2010**, 303; b) M. S. Chen, M. C. White, *Science* **2007**, 318, 783; c) M. Rueda-Becerril, C. C. Sazepin, J. C. T. Leung, T. Okbinoglu, P. Kennepohl, J.-F. Paquins, G. M. Sammis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, 134, 4026.
- [311] a) M. A. Cismesia, S. J. Ryan, D. C. Bland, M. S. Sanford, *J. Org. Chem.* **2017**, 10.1021/acs.joc.7b0048; b) S. D. Schimler, M. A. Cismesia, P. S. Hanley, R. D. J. Froese, M. J. Jansma, D. C. Bland, M. S. Sanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, 139, 1452; c) S. D. Schimler, S. J. Ryan, D. C. Bland, J. E. Anderson, M. S. Sanford, *J. Org. Chem.* **2015**, 80, 12137; d) S. J. Ryan, S. D. Schimler, D. C. Bland, M. S. Sanford, *Org. Lett.* **2015**, 17, 1866; e) N. Ichiishi, A. J. Canty, B. F. Yates, M. S. Sanford, *Organometallics* **2014**, 33, 5525; f) A. F. Brooks, J. J. Topczewski, N. Ichiishi, M. S. Sanford, P. J. H. Scott, *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, 5, 4545; g) L. J. Allen, S. H. Lee, Y. Cheng, P. S. Hanley, J. M. Muhuhi, E. Kane, S. L. Powers, J. E. Anderson, B. M. Bell, G. A. Roth et al., *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2014**, 18, 1045; h) L. J. Allen, J. M. Muhuhi, D. C. Bland, R. Merzel, M. S. Sanford, *J. Org. Chem.* **2014**, 79, 5827; i) Y. Ye, S. D. Schimler, P. S. Hanley, M. S. Sanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, 135, 16292; j) N. Ichiishi, A. J. Canty, B. F. Yates, M. S. Sanford, *Org. Lett.* **2013**, 15, 5134; k) Y. Ye, M. S. Sanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, 135, 4648; l) K. B. McMurtrey, J. M. Racowski, M. S. Sanford, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, 14, 4094.
- [312] S. Bloom, C. R. Pitts, D. C. Miller, N. Haselton, M. G. Holl, E. Urheim, T. Lectka, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, 51, 10580.
- [313] S. Bloom, J. L. Knippel, T. Lectka, *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, 5, 1175.
- [314] S. Bloom, C. R. Pitts, R. Woltornist, A. Griswold, M. G. Holl, T. Lectka, *Org. Lett.* **2013**, 15, 1722.
- [315] J.-B. Xia, C. Zhu, C. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, 135, 17494.

REVIEW

Visible light has evolved into a widely used reagent for many types of transformations in organic synthesis. Are photocatalytic reactions better, different or even unique? We discuss selected classes of reactions for which classical and photocatalytic variants have been reported and try to highlight differences and advantages using visible light irradiation.

Leyre Marzo, Santosh K. Pagire, Oliver Reiser, and Burkhard König**

Page No. – Page No.

Visible-Light Photocatalysis: It does make a Difference in Organic synthesis!